

HarvRESt
Greener Farming with RES

D3.1

HarvRESt strategy for multi-actor engagement and awareness creation in agro communities

First version

27 / 09 / 2024

Funded by
the European Union

www.harvrest.eu

PROJECT INFORMATION

ACRONYM	HarvRESt
PROJECT NAME	Harnessing the vast potential of RES for sustainable farming
PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-7
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
PROJECT NUMBER	101136904
START DAY	1 January 2024
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	D3.1 HarvRESt strategy for multi-actor engagement and awareness creation in agro communities
WORK PACKAGE	WP3
TASK	T3.1
LEAD PARTNER	WR
CONTRIBUTORS	BETA, NORCE, ENG, VdV, ACSA-Sorigué, TCA, CONFAGRI, GCE, FBCD, CKIC
MAIN AUTHORS	Nina Louvrou (WR), Alba Granados Agüero (WR), Dimitrios Chapizanis (WR)
DATE	18 / 09 / 2024
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	Public

DOCUMENT HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	CHANGES	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER
0.1	06/08/2024	NA	WR
0.2	18/09/2024	Feedback	All partners involved
0.3	24/09/2024	Updates	WR
1.0	27/09/2024	Format changes	CIRCE

Disclaimer

The project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

HarvREST's methodology (GA No 101136904) for the stakeholder engagement strategy builds on existing expertise, tools, and templates developed internally by White Research while also considering European Commission guidelines and best practices available in the literature. Part of the standard methodology adopted has already been developed in previous research projects where White Research was a beneficiary, such as the iPRODUCE (GA No. 870037) project. This approach ensures optimal resource allocation, uniformity and adherence to project requirements. *Ad hoc* and tailored modifications were integrated into the methodology used by HarvREST to comply with GA conditions, EU recommendations and project specificities. This report presents the adjusted methodology as it was further developed and applied within HarvREST.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
2.	INTRODUCTION	9
	2.1 Importance of multi-actor stakeholder engagement for RES integration in the agro context.....	9
	2.2 General objectives, engagement principles, and scope of multi-actor engagement	9
	2.3 Structure of the deliverable	10
	2.4 Connection with other tasks	10
	2.5 Upcoming deliverable	11
3.	METHODOLOGY.....	12
	3.1 Stakeholder identification and classification	12
	3.2 Common engagement activities across all Use Cases.....	14
	3.2.1 Warm-up events.....	15
	3.2.2 Awareness-raising campaigns	16
	3.2.3 Capacity building towards the uptake of HarvREST outcomes for RES integration at the farm level	16
	3.2.4 Other workshops and co-creation activities within the project duration.....	17
	3.3 Process and Timeline	17
4.	USE CASES-BASED STRATEGY FOR STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	19
	4.1 Italy – FSDC.....	19
	4.1.1 Current situation.....	19
	4.1.2 Local Stakeholder Ecosystem	19
	4.1.3 Strategy for Stakeholder Engagement (Per Stakeholder Group).....	20
	4.1.4 Action Plan.....	25
	4.2 Denmark – CT	25
	4.2.1 Current situation.....	25
	4.2.2 Local Stakeholder Ecosystem	26
	4.2.3 Strategy for stakeholder engagement (per stakeholder group).....	26
	4.2.4 Action Plan.....	28

4.3	Spain – VdV.....	29
	4.3.1Current situation.....	29
	4.3.2Local Stakeholder Ecosystem	29
	4.3.3Strategy for stakeholder engagement (per stakeholder group)	30
	4.3.4Action Plan.....	32
4.4	Spain - ACSA-Sorigué	33
	4.4.1Current situation.....	33
	4.4.2Local Stakeholder Ecosystem	33
	4.4.3Strategy for stakeholder engagement (per stakeholder group)	34
	4.4.4Action Plan.....	37
4.5	Norway – GGE	37
	4.5.1Current situation.....	37
	4.5.2Local Stakeholder Ecosystem	38
	4.5.3Strategy for stakeholder engagement (per stakeholder group)	38
	4.5.4Action Plan.....	41
5.	CONCLUSIONS, MONITORING AND NEXT STEPS	42
6.	REFERENCES	43
7.	ANNEXES	44
7.1	Stakeholder groups identification template	44
7.2	Warm-up events - Guidelines	47
	7.2.1Task description.....	47
	7.2.2Warm-up objectives.....	47
	7.2.3Action plan for the warm-up events.....	48
	7.2.4Before the event.....	48
	7.2.5Ideas for types of events.....	49
	7.2.6Audience of warm-up events	50
	7.2.7Invitation Criteria.....	52
	7.2.8Invitation process	52
	7.2.9Physical/Virtual Location.....	52
	7.2.10 Holding the event	53

7.2.11	After the event – Reporting Template.....	55
7.2.12	GDPR – Informed Consent Form	55
7.2.13	Brainstorming material ideas	57
7.3	Warm-up events - Reporting template	59

ABBREVIATIONS

ARC	Awareness-Raising Campaigns
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MCDA	Multi Criteria Decision Analysis
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PV	Photovoltaic
Q&A	Questions and Answers
R&D	Research and Development
RES	Renewable Energy Systems
ROI	Return On Investment
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report outlines the concept, methodology, and key actions for developing HarvRESt stakeholder engagement strategies in Italy, Denmark, Spain-VdV, Spain-ACSA-Sorigué, and Norway. It builds on the experience of HarvRESt local partners and previous project insights to design pilot-based strategies that will guide the stakeholder engagement process.

The strategy includes organising warm-up events, awareness campaigns and capacity-building sessions to facilitate knowledge sharing and support. Engagement formats, channels, and additional suggested activities (e.g., farm visits, policy workshops, newsletters etc.,) have been tailored to each stakeholder group, addressing their unique needs and motivations. Each HarvRESt Use Case features distinct objectives and strategies, reflecting regional contexts and stakeholder ecosystems. These tailored approaches aim to promote the adoption and integration of renewable energy systems (RES) in agriculture, and foster collaboration among farmers, energy cooperatives, public authorities, and local energy industries.

The report details the methodology for stakeholder identification and classification, ensuring strategies are customised to community needs. Objectives include providing suggestions on engagement activities, stakeholder consultation, measurable targets, and continuous communication. The strategies will be results-driven and flexible to accommodate unforeseen developments, such as new key stakeholders or ineffective channels. Monitoring and updates will be conducted to ensure optimal implementation and address any issues, with further refinements to be included in deliverable D3.5, based on project experience.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 Importance of multi-actor stakeholder engagement for RES integration in the agro context

Multi-actor engagement is crucial in landscape initiatives, particularly in integrating RES in agriculture, as it fosters a collaborative approach to addressing complex multifaceted challenges. By involving diverse stakeholders such as farmers, energy providers, policymakers, researchers, and community members, multi-actor engagement ensures that multiple perspectives are considered, leading to more comprehensive and sustainable solutions. This inclusive approach helps to align the interests and expertise of various parties, facilitating the development of innovative strategies that balance agricultural productivity with energy sustainability [1]. Furthermore, it enhances the legitimacy and acceptance of landscape initiatives, as stakeholders who are actively involved in the decision-making process are more likely to support and contribute to the successful implementation of these projects [2].

Moreover, multi-actor engagement enables the sharing of resources, knowledge, and best practices, which can significantly enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of integrating RES in agriculture [3]. Collaborative networks can leverage the strengths of each participant, fostering an environment of continuous learning and adaptation. For instance, farmers can gain access to new technologies and practices that improve energy efficiency and crop yield, while energy providers can benefit from insights into sustainable land management. Policymakers can develop more informed and targeted regulations that support both agricultural and energy goals. By breaking down silos and encouraging cross-sector collaboration, multi-actor engagement promotes resilience and innovation, ultimately contributing to the sustainable development of rural landscapes.

2.2 General objectives, engagement principles, and scope of multi-actor engagement

Leading to an increased uptake of RES in the agricultural sector requires the active involvement of key stakeholders. To achieve this, a multi-actor approach is followed when designing the HarvRESt stakeholder engagement strategy. Multi-stakeholder engagement processes together with co-creation activities are among the key pillars of HarvRESt. The multi-actor approach ensures that diverse perspectives and expertise are integrated into the strategy, fostering a collaborative environment where all relevant parties, including farmers, energy cooperatives, agricultural associations, public authorities, and energy industries, work together towards common goals. By actively engaging these stakeholders, HarvRESt aims to create a supportive network that promotes the adoption and integration of RES at the farm level. The co-creation activities facilitate direct participation and input from local actors, ensuring that the strategies developed are tailored to the specific needs and conditions of each community. These activities also promote innovation and the sharing of best practices, further enhancing the effectiveness and sustainability of RES initiatives.

In this context, it is crucial to have a clear understanding of the needs and motivations of local communities, in order to successfully engage them. This report leverages the findings of D2.1, as well as knowledge gained through other activities of the project, to define specific engagement strategies per UC and per targeted stakeholder group.

To this end, this deliverable aims to describe a set of engagement strategies tailored to each UC, that will guide the actions of the consortium for integrating key stakeholders in the HarvRESt activities. A set of strategic

objectives has been defined for all partners to pursue within a context of mutual collaboration, information exchange, and constant reporting. The objectives of the HarvRESt stakeholder engagement approach are:

- Identify the stakeholder groups to be engaged and integrated into the strategy.
- Provide timely and appropriate information to ensure equal, informed, and open participation in the project by stakeholder groups.
- Outline a robust set of engagement activities, to be coherently followed by each UC within the framework of HarvRESt.
- Consult and interact with relevant stakeholder groups.
- Develop a set of measurable, ambitious, and realistic targets to enable the consortium to measure the success of the action plans.
- Disclose and disseminate the anticipated impacts of the project and related mitigation measures if needed.
- Continuously provide information about the project implementation process to the public and government agencies.
- Offer a robust reporting framework for the engagement activities that partners are expected to follow.
- Facilitate open and continuous communication and consultation between various groups, including construction contractors, stakeholders, and the general public.

These objectives will be met through the implementation of the pilot-based strategies that are presented in detail in Chapter 3. Next, the methodology for stakeholder identification and classification is described.

2.3 Structure of the deliverable

D3.1 is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 describes the background and objectives of the deliverable
- Chapter 2 presents the methodology followed for stakeholder identification and classification
- Chapter 3 formulates the stakeholder engagement strategies per Use Case
- Chapter 4 presents the monitoring and evaluation framework of the engagement process.

2.4 Connection with other tasks

Due to the horizontal nature of engagement, this deliverable is connected with several WPs of the project (Figure 1). Specifically, the content of this deliverable is linked to the outcomes of Task 2.2, where an assessment of the needs of local stakeholders in each UC and an analysis of the framework conditions in the EU, national, and regional contexts of the HarvRESt UCs took place. Additionally, Task 2.5 working groups support the implementation of the stakeholder engagement multi-actor approach.

Figure 1. Interconnections between T3.1 and HarvRESt workplan

These tasks complement each other in identifying the stakeholders and their respective needs and motivations. The results of Task 3.1 will feed into:

- T3.2 Design of tailored awareness-raising activities per UC,
- T3.4 Capacity building towards the uptake of HarvRESt outcomes for RES integration supporting each HarvRESt farm,
- T6.4 Co-creation sessions, experimental trials, and final validation of each HarvRESt UC,
- T7.2 Development of guidelines for agro-communities' business models and the relevant workshops,
- T7.3 Strategy for advising and providing technical guidance on EU legislation and policy recommendations and the relevant policy sessions.

2.5 Upcoming deliverable

An updated version of this report, “D3.5 HarvRESt strategy for multi-actor engagement and awareness creation in agro communities (final version)”, is expected to be delivered in M30. The goal of D3.5 will be to provide an updated version of the strategies and action plans implemented in each UC if changes have been made, based on the experience gained through the project activities. At the same time, the report will present any required adjustments, and the progress that has been made in terms of engagement for each UC and will provide an overall assessment of the engagement strategies employed for RES uptake at HarvRESt farms.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Stakeholder identification and classification

The first step in designing a stakeholder engagement strategy is identifying the key stakeholders with whom the HarvRESt Use Cases partners will establish channels of communication and collaboration. In this context, by stakeholders, we mean either individuals or groups who are going to be impacted, to a greater or lesser extent, by the project's outcomes and who, therefore, may have an interest or stake in the project's design and implementation.

For this purpose, a template for stakeholder mapping has been circulated to the consortium (see Annex 7.1) and all UC partners involved have been asked to provide information about their local ecosystem of stakeholders. Based on a thorough needs analysis of the HarvRESt activities and workplan, an initial list of the HarvRESt project's stakeholder groups was formulated in this template, which was then updated based on partners' input (Table 1). The stakeholder groups are divided into subgroups to facilitate the identification of potential targets, however, the subgroups are indicative and not all of them are necessarily going to be engaged in the project activities. It is noted that the engagement actions are dynamic and the stakeholder groups to be engaged may be updated during project implementation to support each Use Case needs.

The stakeholder identification process will be reassessed frequently throughout the project, in order to ensure that no groups or individuals have been missed. This may involve identifying new stakeholders that need to be engaged during the project or as stakeholder needs and priorities change over the course of implementation. It is important to ensure that groups or individuals who are considered to be potential sources of conflict are not left out of the engagement process simply because they have opposing views.

At the same time, the Task 2.5 definition of working groups comprised of local stakeholders within each UC will support the project execution through a multi-actor approach.

Following the initial identification of the stakeholder groups and subgroups, the relevant partners had the opportunity to rate the influence and impact of the identified stakeholder groups to assist the stakeholder categorisation process which is further elaborated in UC subsections of Chapter 4.

Table 1. HarvRESt Stakeholder Ecosystem

Stakeholder Group	Stakeholder Subgroup
G1: Industry	Energy sector companies
	Transport companies
	Investors & agro-entrepreneurs
	SMEs and micro-enterprises
	Technology providers
	Medium and large-sized energy industries
	Primary producers, energy end users
	Agriculture machinery private sector
G2: Agri-sector	Local value chain actors
	Farmers
	Livestock Industry Representatives
G3: Academia and scientific community	Individual researchers
	Research organisations
	R&D units in private companies
	Universities
G4: Civil society	General public
	Citizen associations
	NGOs
	Civil Society Associations
	Environmental Associations
	Energy communities/RESCoops
	Agricultural Associations/cooperatives
	Clusters & Sectorial organisations
G5: Policymakers	Regional authorities
	Local authorities (e.g. municipalities)
	National ministries
	National / EU agencies
	Parties / Parliament Advisors / European Associations
	Agricultural Sustainability Advocates
Other	1.500 Climate Pilot Farms
	Research projects
	Regional/local media outlets
	EU-funded initiatives

The different stakeholder groups have been mapped in a matrix using as a basis the EC's Toolkit for the evaluation of communication activities (2017)¹. The matrix (Figure 2) can help visualise and determine the level of importance of the stakeholders and is based on two dimensions:

- **Influence** refers to the capacity of a stakeholder to affect the achievement of the project results. For instance, stakeholders have a high level of influence if they control technical, financial, scientific or human resources that are needed to implement some activities.
- **Impact** refers to the effect the project has on each specific group of stakeholders.

Building upon this classification, pilot-based strategies for stakeholder engagement have been developed and are presented below, focusing on the specific context and needs of each UC.

Figure 2. HarvRESt Stakeholder classification matrix

3.2 Common engagement activities across all Use Cases

The HarvRESt engagement strategies are developed at a pilot level, aiming to better address the specific scope and challenges of each UC. Each UC has a different focus not only in terms of agricultural activity and RE type(s), but also in terms of composition and maturity. However, there are some common goals for all strategies which are:

¹ European Commission, 2017. Toolkit for the evaluation of the communication activities. Directorate General for Communication. V. February 2017. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2019-10/communication-evaluation-toolkit_en.pdf

- Identify understanding and knowledge gaps, increase awareness, and boost acceptance of RES within local farming communities.
- Facilitate knowledge sharing, good practices exchange, and networking among different stakeholder groups.
- Increase the willingness of stakeholders to actively participate in activities related to RES within and beyond the context of the HarvRESt project.

Based on these goals, the engagement strategies that have been developed for each UC are presented below, outlining the scope and composition and the targeted stakeholder groups. A set of suggestions on engagement channels that will be deployed in each UC in the form of activities and events are presented.

3.2.1 Warm-up events

The warm-up events are envisioned as dynamic and diverse engagement moments with the main goal of promoting HarvRESt’s vision and attracting further mobilisation of key local actors. The warm-up events will be the basis for subsequent project activities such as the awareness-raising campaigns (T3.2), guaranteeing a cohesive and impactful engagement process across all HarvRESt Use Cases. The overall objectives of the warm-up events are to i) **introduce HarvRESt** in each of the local Use Case areas, ii) **foster stakeholder engagement** and **attract further mobilisation** of the local actors, iii) **promote knowledge sharing** and exchange by disseminating best practices and showcasing HarvRESt solutions and technologies, and iv) **promote networking** by initiating or reinforcing existing collaboration and synergies.

Following HarvRESt’s Grant Agreement (GA), at least **two rounds of warm-up events must be organised by local partners in each Use Case:**

- The first round of warm-up events will mainly focus on engaging local stakeholders, introducing them to the project and its vision and collecting feedback from the local community to better steer the project and align it with regional needs.
- The second round will be enhanced with the presentation of some key project results and further engagement in fruitful discussions. Ideally, the second round will take place once the project has generated some initial results to update the stakeholders involved about HarvRESt’s progress.

As the leader of WP3, WR developed comprehensive guidelines to organise the warm-up events (Table 2). The Guidelines provided detailed information on the nature of the warm-up events, their objectives, how to organise the sessions, identify the right stakeholders, etc. Finally, WR prepared a Reporting Template to be used by all Use Cases and their RTOs to capture the main takeaways of each warm-up event. Both the Guidelines and the Reporting template can be found in Annex 7.2 and 7.3 respectively.

Table 2. Action plan for the warm-up events for all HarvRESt Use Cases

Action	Who	When
Share event plan and agenda (4 – 6 weeks before each event)	All Use Cases & RTOs	M7 – M18 (1 st Round) M18 – M27 (2 nd Round)
Event organisation and implementation phase	All Use Cases & RTOs	M7 – M18 (1 st Round) M18 – M27 (2 nd Round)
Fill out workshop reporting templates and send them to WR	All Use Cases & RTOs	Max 2 weeks after the warm-up

3.2.2 Awareness-raising campaigns

The awareness-raising campaigns (ARC) in the context of Task 3.2² will be meticulously designed to foster the adoption of RES in the UC HarvRESt agricultural settings (Table 3). The methodological approach will start by integrating the output from Task 2.2 (D2.1), which provides a foundation for UC framework conditions and different stakeholder groups’ needs and perceptions. This will be followed by a co-design and creative series of brainstorming sessions, ensuring a collaborative and inclusive strategy development process. The tailored design and specification of interventions are crafted based on the insights gathered, **aiming to address the unique needs and challenges of each UC and its target groups.**

The implementation phase involves rolling out awareness-raising campaigns at the Use Case level. These campaigns will employ various formats online and offline, with material such as flyers, social media posts, and infographics to effectively communicate the benefits of RES adoption. Additionally, there is a close collaboration with FBCD (Dissemination Manager) for executing online campaigns across social media platforms. This multi-faceted approach ensures that the messaging is not only widespread but also tailored to resonate with different stakeholder groups and cultural contexts. During the period M10 to M30, these campaigns will be further designed, deployed and reported in D3.5 HarvRESt strategy for multi-actor engagement and awareness creation in agro-communities (final version) - M30.

Table 3. Action plan for the Awareness Raising campaigns for all HarvRESt Use Cases

Action	Who	When
Preparatory Phase (including brainstorming sessions)	All Use Cases & RTOs	M10-M13
Design Campaigns	All Use Cases & RTOs	M13-M15
Deployment of awareness-raising campaigns and reporting templates completed	All Use Cases & RTOs	M15 - M27
Implemented activities reported in D3.5	WR	M30

3.2.3 Capacity building towards the uptake of HarvRESt outcomes for RES integration at the farm level

Within the framework of T3.4 (M13 – M30), WR will lead the preparation of capacity-building material aiming at empowering farmers and rural actors with skills and knowledge on RES. To achieve this, an analysis of training needs will be performed based on previous project results such as D3.1, D2.1, etc. and complementary desk research. This needs’ analysis will allow us to identify current skills, perceptions, and knowledge gaps at the Use Case level. A training workshop will take place at each Use Case, implemented by each Use case RTO with the support of the Use Case leaders. The goal of the **capacity-building program** will be to empower farmers and rural actors to leverage the HarvRESt assets and services related to the technical, environmental, financial, regulatory, business and stakeholder engagement aspects of RES uptake at farms.

Capacity-building material will be prepared based on the results of the needs analysis led by WR. Under the coordination of WR, training content will be drafted by the project’s experts and adjusted to the specificities of each Use Case. CIRCE, BETA, and Suite5 will cover technical, environmental, and sustainability aspects; CKIC

² T3.2 starts at M10 (October 2024) yet as the GA mentions, the methodology of awareness-raising campaigns is expected to be reported in D3.1. However, D3.1 is due by M9 (September 2024) which is before T3.2 officially begins. This was identified as a proposal typo during the Kick-off Meeting and will be addressed during the first GA’s amendment.

policy-relevant material, EnGreen business and innovation aspects; and WR on stakeholder engagement and market research. The capacity-building material will be tailored to each Use Case and the capacity-building workshop will take place during the period of M13 (January 2025) and M30 (June 2026), considering the preparation and implementation phase. The process and results of this task will be reported in D3.3 (M30) and Table 4 details the preliminary action plan foreseen to achieve this goal.

Table 4. Action Plan for the Capacity Building Program for all HarvRESt Use Cases

Action	Who	When
Preparatory Phase (training needs analysis)	WR, CIRCE, BETA, Suite5, CKIC, ENG, and all Use Cases & RTOs	M13 – M16
Preparation of capacity-building modules	WR, CIRCE, BETA, Suite5, CKIC, ENG	M16 – M19
Implementation and reporting of training workshops carried out by RTOs	All Use Cases & RTOs	M19 - M27
D3.3 HarvRESt capacity building material	WR	M30

3.2.4 Other workshops and co-creation activities within the project duration

Other workshops and co-creation sessions, foreseen in the HarvRESt Grant Agreement at the UC level, will be organised during the project duration to bring together relevant stakeholders to discuss critical aspects around the topic of RES integration:

- Co-creation sessions for the definition of KPI criteria will be conducted in the context of T6.2 “Co-creation on procedures and weighting criteria for the MCDA”.
- A final Co-creation session to discuss the recommendations from the HarvRESt Decision Support System and business catalogue will take place in the context of T6.4 “Co-creation sessions, experimental trials and final validation of HarvRESt use cases”.
- A workshop to present business models to key stakeholders will be organised in the context of T7.2 “Development of guidelines for agro-communities business models”.
- Policy sessions, as part of T7.3, for the upscaling of HarvRESt’s solutions and formulations of policy pathways and financing mechanisms.

3.3 Process and Timeline

The initial design of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategies for promoting the uptake of RES at farms followed a meticulously planned process. This approach ensured that the strategies were continuously refined and adapted based on stakeholder input and emerging insights. Following the initial step of stakeholder identification and classification process, which was critical for identifying key players and understanding their roles, interests, and potential influence on the project, a series of bilateral calls were then conducted with representatives from each UC. These calls served multiple purposes, including information gathering, relationship building, and collecting preliminary feedback on the proposed engagement strategies, thereby laying the groundwork for effective collaboration.

Based on the insights gained from these bilateral calls, initial drafts of the UC Stakeholder Engagement Strategies were prepared. These drafts outlined the **objectives and nature of the stakeholder engagement activities**, the **transversal-core activities** (such as warm-up events, awareness-raising campaigns etc.), the

main **stakeholder groups** to be engaged, the key **engagement opportunities**, and general **strategies to avoid stakeholder fatigue** while engaging each stakeholder group effectively. To ensure ongoing stakeholder involvement and continuous improvement of the engagement strategies, a **permanent feedback loop** was established. This loop included regular ad-hoc interactions with the UCs and adaptive adjustments to the strategies based on UC input.

4. USE CASES-BASED STRATEGY FOR STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Each Use Case's stakeholder strategy provides an overview of suggested activities beyond the core ones—such as warm-ups and awareness-raising campaigns—detailed in section 3.2. The key messages and suggested formats for each stakeholder group outlined here can also be incorporated into these core activities, ensuring that all engagement efforts are aligned and reinforcing the project's objectives.

4.1 Italy – FSDC

4.1.1 Current situation

Besides the HarvRESt basic engagement goals, the Italian use case aims more specifically to explore joint models for promoting RES in agro communities and along the food value chain. The focus is on studying agronomic practices for crops grown under photovoltaic panels, investigating new business models, promoting sustainability through **carbon credit certifications**, and developing **training workshops/educational pathways** that integrate technology and RES into modern farming practices. The stakeholder engagement strategy for the UC is designed to address the specific needs and interests of various stakeholder groups. The vision for stakeholder engagement in the Italy Use Case is to promote the adoption of RES by **disseminating the results among a wide range of stakeholders, with a special emphasis on farmers**. To promote RES adoption through comprehensive stakeholder engagement, emphasising education, partnership building, and policy advocacy.

The Italian UC is composed of four partners as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Composition of the Italian UC

Partner	Stakeholder group	Role in the project
Fattoria Solidale Del Circeo (FSDC)	Social Cooperative that deals with the employment of people with disabilities by doing organic farming	Use Case
EnGreen (EnG)	Energy consulting company	Supporter RTO
Confagricoltura (CONFAGRI)	Collective organisation of Farmers in Italy	Supporter RTO
Tecnoalimenti (TCA)	Scientific and Technological Research Organisation for Innovation, consultancy and certification	Supporter RTO

4.1.2 Local Stakeholder Ecosystem

The local stakeholder ecosystem includes a diverse range of actors, each playing a crucial role in the adoption and success of RES in agriculture. **Investors and agro-entrepreneurs** are leading stakeholders who prioritise return on investment (ROI) and risk mitigation through RES investments. **Energy companies and Technology providers** and suppliers of agricultural machinery offer essential RES-compatible technologies necessary for effective implementation on farms. **Farmers, local value chain actors, and representatives from the livestock industry** focus on sustainable farming practices and environmental stewardship. **Research organisations** contribute technical insights and support innovation in RES adoption through research and education. **Environmental associations and Energy communities/RESCoops** advocate for a more diversified and resilient RE market, and support policies that promote RES initiatives. **Public authorities**, including municipalities, policymakers and regulators, influence RES adoption through incentives and regulatory frameworks. **Citizen associations and NGOs** can demonstrate a positive attitude towards RES integration and foster the promotion of these technologies.

4.1.3 Strategy for Stakeholder Engagement (Per Stakeholder Group)

The strategy for stakeholder engagement in the Italian UC follows a multi-stakeholder approach to meet the specific needs of each involved group. With the aim to motivate and bring together different stakeholder groups to participate in project activities, it describes specific incentives and contributions that correspond to each stakeholder group.

Investors & Agro-entrepreneurs

The motivation of this group to participate can be sparked by indicating the chance to explore financial opportunities presented by RE solutions and gain further knowledge on methods and tools for RES uptake at farms. By showcasing the potential for high returns on investment, the project will demonstrate how adopting RES, such as agrivoltaics, can significantly enhance farm profitability. Additionally, the project will emphasise strategies for mitigating risks associated with these investments, providing a sense of security and confidence to stakeholders. Detailed insights and examples of successful implementations will further illustrate how integrating renewable energy into agricultural practices not only boosts financial performance but also promotes long-term sustainability.

The first step is to raise awareness among this relevant stakeholder group through an **informative e-mail**. Arousing their interest in the HarvRESt project will be achieved by offering concrete information on the benefits for those deciding to join the project activities and, namely, by presenting them the future opportunities for collaborations with other relevant actors. To this end, the **promotional material of the project** and the **dissemination channels** of the project (website, social media accounts, newsletters etc.,) can be used.

Key Messages:

- Emphasise the **potential for high returns** on investment and the strategies available for mitigating risks associated with RES.
- Provide detailed **insights and examples into how agrivoltaic systems** can enhance farm profitability and sustainability.

The next step in the engagement process involves interaction and information exchange between them and the UC mainly at the local level. More specifically, **warm-up events (T3.1)**, **awareness-raising activities (T3.2)** and **training workshops (T3.4)** will help us communicate with the investors and receive information about their needs as well as their feedback on the processes to be followed.

During the warm-up events and awareness-raising activities, **investment opportunities** can be discussed, aiming to explore the potential financial benefits and operational aspects of RES investments. The activities will facilitate **networking opportunities** with successful RES adopters and **present real-world examples** and **success stories** of RES projects to illustrate tangible benefits and practical applications.

Energy companies and Technology providers

The motivation of energy sector stakeholders and technology providers to join the Italian UC can be triggered through demonstrating the economic and social benefits of RES application at the farm level. The **first step** of communication will address the technology providers and industrial stakeholders with an **informative e-mail** or a **one-to-one meeting**, pointing out the potential of RES uptake at farms as well as the methodologies and approaches proposed by the project.

Key Messages:

- **Showcase technological advancements and integration potential:** Highlight how the latest advancements in RES technologies can be seamlessly integrated into existing agricultural systems, improving efficiency and productivity.
- **Economic and operational benefits:** Emphasise the cost-effectiveness, operational efficiency, and long-term sustainability benefits of adopting RES technologies.
- **Collaboration opportunities:** Present opportunities for partnerships and collaborations that can drive innovation and growth within the industry.

Following this, the next step of their engagement process includes interaction and information exchange between them and the UC mainly on the local level. More specifically, **warm-up events (T3.1)**, **awareness-raising activities (T3.2)** and **training workshops (T3.4)** will help us communicate with the Technology Providers and Industry actors and receive information about their individual needs as well as their feedback on the RES integration processes to be followed. The training workshops will allow stakeholders to participate in **detailed sessions focusing on the technical aspects and operational integration of RES technologies**. These sessions can be tailored to different levels of technical expertise. The warm-up events will facilitate **roundtables/sessions that bring together technology providers, industry actors, and agricultural stakeholders to discuss innovations, challenges, and collaboration opportunities**. These events can focus on identifying common goals, sharing best practices, and exploring new partnership opportunities. In the context of the awareness-raising campaign actions, **farm visits** can be organised to showcase practical applications of RES on working farms, and to hear firsthand success stories of local farmers who have successfully integrated RES.

Farmers/Local Value Chain Actors, Livestock Industry Representatives

The primary motivation of Local Value Chain Actors and Farmers for engaging with the Italian UC activities is to **broaden their knowledge of RES application and potential**. They will have the chance to share their knowledge and establish collaborations with different types of stakeholders while providing insights into the project's activities and helping produce tangible results, applicable to real-life cases.

The first step for the engagement of local value chain actors and farmers is to create awareness about the project, the benefits of RES use at farms and the Italian UC. To this end, the **promotional material** of the project and the dissemination channels of the project (website, social media accounts, etc.), as well as **word of mouth** and **press releases** in sector magazines can be employed. The UC team's close connections to farmers can facilitate these initial interactions. The dissemination material of the project will be adjusted according to local stakeholders' needs, with any complex meanings translated into an **easy-to-grasp language for farmers and rural actors to resonate with**. The aim is to describe the overall scope of the UC and explain, in simple terms, how RES can benefit the economy, environment and society at a local level.

Key Messages:

- **RES can significantly reduce operational costs and improve energy independence:** Emphasise how renewable energy sources can lower energy expenses and reduce dependency on external providers, improving financial stability and self-sufficiency on farms.

- **Implementing RES can enhance farm sustainability and productivity:** Highlight how the integration of RE technologies can improve overall farm efficiency, supporting long-term sustainability and increased productivity.
- **Government incentives and support are available for adopting RES technologies:** Inform farmers and stakeholders about the various subsidies, tax credits, and financial incentives offered by the government to encourage the adoption of RES.
- **Synergies between agrivoltaics and biodiversity boosting:** Stress how combining agricultural practices with RES like agrivoltaics can not only benefit energy efficiency but also promote ecological balance, boosting biodiversity and supporting wildlife-friendly farming systems.

The next step for the engagement of Local Value Chain Actors and Farmers will be to invite them to participate in **-ideally, face-to-face- activities, such as the warm-up events (T3.1), awareness-raising activities (T3.2) and training workshops (T3.4)** that will bring together stakeholders' relevant to RES uptake at farms. These sessions can also be used to collect feedback on the HarvREST tools and methodologies. Overall, it is important to keep this stakeholder group regularly updated with the progress and the activities of the UC, providing opportunities for the exchange of knowledge and skills through training but also less formal ways of interaction.

In the context of the Italian UC awareness-raising campaign, **farm visits** can be organised to showcase practical applications of RES on working farms, and to hear firsthand **success stories of local farmers** who have successfully integrated RES. Participation of the UC team in **agricultural fairs** can also help engage a broader audience of farmers and agri-sector stakeholders. Additionally, launching a **survey or set of interviews** can allow for the collection of detailed feedback, opinions, and insights directly from rural actors, helping to tailor the project's approach to meet their specific needs and concerns.

Research organisations

The engagement of research organisations is important for the creation of synergies and the involvement of researchers and students in fostering RES uptake at farms. By highlighting research opportunities in agrivoltaics and sustainable farming practices, the project can attract **collaborations on new studies and innovations**. Furthermore, research organisations will have **access to project data, findings, and practical applications**, providing a rich resource for further research and contributing to the **development of innovative solutions** that support sustainable agriculture.

Key Messages:

- Research opportunities in agrivoltaics and sustainable farming practices.
- Potential for collaboration on new studies and innovations.
- Access to project data, findings, and practical applications for further research.

The first step is to raise awareness to the research organisations through an informative e-mail to them. Arousing their interest in the HarvREST project will be achieved by offering concrete information on the benefits for those deciding to join the project activities and, namely, by presenting them the future opportunities for collaborations with other relevant actors. Further interaction through invitations to the project **warm-up events (T3.1), awareness-raising activities (T3.2) and training workshops (T3.4)** is foreseen. In the context of the Italian UC awareness-raising campaign, the academic and research community can be

further engaged through **networking opportunities**, which would foster **collaboration and knowledge exchange** in the field of agrivoltaics and RES integration at farms.

Environmental associations and Energy communities/RESCoops

The motivation of Energy Communities and RESCoops to engage in the Italian UC activities can be fostered by emphasising the community and economic advantages of RES adoption. The initial step in communication can be through a **detailed letter or email**, outlining HarvREST's vision, goals, and the specific objectives of the UC. This initial outreach will focus on two main objectives: first, to share insights on RES and HarvREST's vision, and second, to encourage their active involvement in the Italian UC activities.

Key Messages:

- Highlight how HarvREST's initiatives contribute to reducing carbon emissions and promoting sustainable farming practices, aligning with the environmental goals of these groups.
- Showcase how participation in HarvREST can empower communities to lead in the transition to renewable energy, creating models of success that can be replicated elsewhere.
- Encourage partnerships between environmental associations, energy communities, and other stakeholders to amplify the impact of sustainable energy projects and environmental stewardship.
- Highlight the opportunity to collaborate with experts and gain access to resources that can enhance the effectiveness of their environmental and energy initiatives.

As part of the Italian UC awareness-raising campaign (T3.2), **farm visits** could be organised to demonstrate the practical use of RES on active farms, allowing participants to hear firsthand **success stories** from local farmers on how RES has positively impacted local communities. In the context of the **training workshops** (T3.4), sessions on the **benefits of RES and more specifically agrivoltaics** can be held to engage energy communities' members and environmental associations. Their participation in the **warm-up events** will facilitate **networking opportunities** with other stakeholder groups, fostering collaboration in RES projects and shared learning across the project.

Regional Authorities, Policymakers

The engagement of public authorities and EU initiatives can significantly support and promote the overall vision of the Italian UC. Local, regional and national authorities will be informed about the UC scope and composition through **online or physical meetings** and **relevant promotional material in the local language** (if available) will be shared. Further communication through email or phone will focus on presenting the results of the co-creation activities, while their invitation to the **project policy sessions (T7.3)** will help identify possible connections and synergies and encourage discussion about relevant policies and investments at the local and EU level.

Key Messages:

- **Economic development and job creation:** Highlight the potential for RES integration to drive regional economic growth and create jobs within the agricultural sector.
- **Regulatory support and streamlined processes:** Emphasise the need for supportive policies and streamlined regulatory processes to facilitate RES adoption.

- **Environmental sustainability and energy independence:** Underline the environmental benefits and the role of RES in enhancing energy independence and meeting sustainability goals.

In the framework of T3.4, **training modules targeting policymakers and regional authorities** can be prepared, focusing on the technical aspects, economic benefits, and regulatory requirements of RES adoption can be organised. These sessions would provide actionable insights and practical guidance to public authorities. Policymakers and regional authorities should be kept informed about the Italian UC updates, indicatively through a series of **newsletters** as part of the awareness-raising campaign (T3.2).

Citizen associations and NGOs

Engaging citizen associations is important for the Italian UC as one of the key objectives of their engagement strategy is to enhance the public's understanding and acceptance of RES. The groups of citizen associations and NGOs will be addressed through the **project dissemination material including press releases, journalistic articles, website, newsletters**. To achieve broad dissemination of the UC scope and activities and increase RES public acceptability, **social media campaigns** through both the project and partners' accounts will take place. For these campaigns, local language can be used together with relevant hashtags that can easily convey key messages. Finally, it is important to note that the use of technical and scientific concepts in communication targeted to the general public should be avoided.

Key Messages:

- RES adoption contributes to environmental sustainability and community resilience.
- Community involvement in RES projects can enhance local economic development.
- Education and awareness are key to driving the transition to renewable energy.

Horizontal Additional engagement formats (optional)

The engagement activities detailed below are not part of the formal project implementation but are the result of two rounds of bilateral discussions and brainstorming sessions with the UC teams and their RTOs. They are intended to strengthen each UC strategy, ensuring their relevance both during and after the project's duration.

Farm visits, demonstration events

Farm visits can be an effective way to engage stakeholders in the context of HarvREST awareness-raising activities (T3.2) by providing a hands-on, immersive experience that highlights the practical benefits of renewable energy solutions in agriculture. These visits allow stakeholders to see firsthand how renewable energy technologies are integrated into farming operations, offering a clear demonstration of their economic and environmental advantages. By interacting directly with successful adopters and observing the impact on productivity and sustainability, stakeholders gain a deeper understanding and appreciation of the potential for renewable energy to transform the agricultural sector. This tangible experience can foster stronger connections, build trust, and inspire greater commitment to the project's goals.

Interviews & Surveys

Interviews and surveys can be highly effective tools for engaging stakeholders in the Italian UC. These methods allow for the collection of detailed feedback, opinions, and insights directly from stakeholders, helping to tailor the project's approach to meet their specific needs and concerns. Interviews provide an opportunity for in-depth discussions, enabling stakeholders to express their views, share experiences, and contribute valuable

ideas that can shape the project's direction. Surveys, on the other hand, can reach a broader audience, gathering quantitative and qualitative data that reflect the diverse perspectives of the stakeholder community. By using interviews and surveys, the project can ensure that stakeholder voices are heard and integrated into the decision-making process, leading to more informed and inclusive strategies. These activities can take place indicatively in the framework of warm-up events (T3.1), and awareness-raising activities (T3.2).

4.1.4 Action Plan

This section sets the time plan for the deployment of the channels and activities that will be used for each of the targeted stakeholders of the Italian UC. The action plan for the stakeholders' engagement in the region is summarised in Table 6.

Table 6. Stakeholders' Engagement Action Plan for the Italian UC

Targeted stakeholder	Channel/Action	Timing
Technology providers, Investors & Agro-entrepreneurs, Research organisations, Citizen associations	Initial e-mail communications and personal interactions (T3.1)	M10-M12
All IT UC stakeholders	First round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M07-M18
All IT UC stakeholders	Second round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M19-M27
All IT UC stakeholders	Awareness-raising campaign (T3.2)	M15-M27
All (particularly farmers, citizen associations)	Capacity building – training workshop (T3.4)	M19-M27
All IT UC stakeholders	Co-creation sessions for the definition of the weighting criteria (T6.2)	M19-M30
All IT UC stakeholders	Final co-creation sessions (T6.4)	M19-M36
All IT UC stakeholders	Use Case working groups (T2.5)	M09-M36
All IT UC stakeholders	Business model workshops (T7.2)	M31-M36
Authorities, Policymakers	Policy sessions (T7.3)	M13-M30

4.2 Denmark – CT

4.2.1 Current situation

The Danish use case focuses on the integration and promotion of biogas technologies in agricultural practices to enhance sustainability and energy efficiency. Denmark's commitment to reducing carbon emissions and increasing renewable energy sources makes biogas a pivotal component in achieving national sustainability targets. The vision is to empower and engage a diverse network of stakeholders to collaboratively advance the implementation and scalability of sustainable biogas solutions, leveraging digital tools and big data to optimise energy production and nutrient management in rural areas.

The Danish UC is composed of these two partners as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Composition of the Danish UC

Partner	Stakeholder group	Role in the project
ConTerra (CT)	Agriculture-related services provider	Use Case
Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (FBCD)	Cluster Organisation	UC Supporter RTO

4.2.2 Local Stakeholder Ecosystem

The stakeholder ecosystem for the Danish use case is diverse and includes energy companies, technology providers, research institutions, and governmental bodies. **Farmers'** engagement is vital for ensuring practical application and widespread support for these technologies. **Energy companies** are at the forefront of innovation in renewable energy technologies and are responsible for implementing pilot projects, making them key drivers in the transition to sustainable energy. **Technology providers** play a crucial role by developing and commercialising clean technologies that enhance energy efficiency and support renewable integration. **Research institutions** contribute significantly by conducting research and development to enhance technological capabilities and address market needs, ensuring that the solutions being implemented are both effective and cutting-edge. **Governmental bodies/Authorities** set the policies and regulations necessary to create a supportive environment for clean technology adoption and provide financial incentives that help drive the market towards renewable energy solutions.

4.2.3 Strategy for stakeholder engagement (per stakeholder group)

The stakeholder engagement strategy for the Danish Use Case is designed to meet the distinct needs of each group through a multi-stakeholder approach. It aims to bring together and motivate various stakeholders to engage in project activities by outlining specific contributions and tailored incentives for each group.

Farmers, agricultural advisers

The primary motivation for farmers to participate in the Danish UC activities is to enhance their understanding of RES applications and to recognise that integrating these technologies into their farming systems, is not only feasible but also offers multiple benefits. The first step of communication with farmers will be to inform them about the project and its overall approach as well as the specific scope of the Danish UC via personal interactions and e-mails. To this end, the promotional material of the project and the communication channels of the project and partners can be used (**newsletters, press releases, social media, and website**). A following step for the engagement of farmers will be to invite them to participate in, ideally face-to-face, **warm-up events (T3.1), training workshops (T3.4), and awareness-raising activities (T3.2)** that will bring together stakeholders relevant to RES uptake at the farm level. The identification and collaboration with respected farmers/local champions who have adopted RES will facilitate the engagement of further relevant actors. In the framework of the training workshops (T3.4), agricultural advisers will be further equipped with **knowledge about the technical aspects of RES integration, and more specifically about the Biogas planning tool** to support farmers. The Danish UC warm-up events and awareness-raising activities (T3.2) will facilitate their **exchanges with technical experts**, and their participation in community meetings and industry events to share their experiences and challenges and improve their understanding of the benefits of RES. **Channels for farmers to provide feedback and express concerns** can be established, including surveys, discussion forums, and follow-up meetings to address any issues and refine the approach based on their input.

Key Messages:

- Emphasise in clear and simple language the tangible benefits of RES, including increased efficiency, cost savings, and environmental stewardship.
- Highlight real-world success stories and the positive impact on local farming practices can help illustrate the value of these systems.

In the context of the Danish UC awareness-raising campaigns (T3.2), **engaging stories and case studies featuring local farmers** who have benefited from RES can be presented in **farm visits and demonstration events**. These narratives can be used in various formats, such as videos, blog posts, and social media updates, and translated into local languages to reach a wider audience.

Through these events, potential early RE adopters and local champions can be identified to further promote the HarvREST approach. The relationships between farmers and the UC team will deepen by involving farmers in the co-design of tools and solutions, providing them with direct benefits and incentives for their participation in HarvREST activities.

Energy companies (Medium and large-sized energy industries)

The motivation of energy companies to join the Danish UC can be triggered through demonstrating the collective benefits of innovative RES applications at the farm level. The Danish UC holds strong connections with industry actors through industry forums and conferences. The first step of communication will address the energy companies with **an informative e-mail or a one-to-one meeting**, pointing out the potential of biogas uptake at farms as well as the business models and overall approach proposed by the project.

Key Messages:

- RES in agriculture offer significant cost savings and efficiency improvements.
- Adopting RES technologies aligns with corporate sustainability goals and regulatory requirements.
- Collaboration in RES initiatives can enhance innovation and market competitiveness.

Following this, the next step of their engagement process includes interaction and information exchange between them and the UC. More specifically, **warm-up events (T3.1), training workshops (T3.4), and awareness-raising activities (T3.2)** will help the UC to communicate with the energy companies, collect data to **tailor the biogas planning tool** to better meet their specific needs and constraints. In the framework of the awareness-raising activities (T3.2), **one-to-one meetings** with energy company representatives can take place to provide personalised consultations to address specific concerns and opportunities. Additionally, the **distribution of detailed reports and data-driven insights on RES benefits** will facilitate collaboration opportunities.

Technology Providers

The main motivation for technology providers to join the Danish UC activities will be to expand their knowledge of the applications of RE technologies at farms. They will have access to success cases, demo events and co-creation sessions (e.g., warm-up events, and training workshops) where HarvREST methods and tools will be presented.

Key Messages:

- Focus on the technical benefits and innovations in biogas technology.
- Emphasise the integration of new technologies to enhance efficiency.
- Highlight the support available for technology adoption.

The first step will be to communicate with technology providers with an **official letter or e-mail**, pointing out the potential of biogas integration at farms, as well as the associated business models. Following this, this group can be further engaged through their participation in the **warm-up events (T3.1)**, **training workshops (T3.4)**, and **awareness-raising activities (T3.2)**. In the context of the training workshops, **specialised sessions that delve into the latest innovations in biogas and RES integration** can be included. These sessions should include detailed presentations on cutting-edge solutions, case studies of successful implementations, and discussions on overcoming technical challenges. The warm-up events and awareness-raising activities serve as platforms for **networking, forming business partnerships**, and demonstrating the practical applications of their technologies to potential customers and investors.

Regional Authorities/Municipalities, Policymakers/ Governmental bodies

The engagement of regional authorities and policymakers will support the uptake of the overall vision of the Danish case and will increase the UC work's impact at the regional level. Great emphasis will be given to the community socioeconomic benefits of RES uptake at farms, as well as to the environmental gains of the HarvREST approach. One key engagement method to be employed will be contacting them via physical or online **one-to-one meetings or e-mails**.

Key Messages:

- Supporting RES adoption aligns with national and regional sustainability goals.
- Policy support can drive innovation and economic growth in the agricultural sector.
- Successful RES projects can serve as models for broader policy initiatives.

The next step will be to directly communicate with relevant departments through email or phone and invite them to participate in the UC activities. Their participation in the **warm-up events (T3.1)**, **awareness-raising activities (T3.2)**, and **training workshops (T3.4)** will be encouraged, as well as in the **policy sessions (T7.3)** which will target representatives of local administration and policymakers. The organisation of **farm visits**, in the context of the Danish UC awareness-raising campaign (T3.2) and the development of **engaging stories and case studies featuring local farmers** who have benefited from RES, can demonstrate the practical benefits and feasibility of RES installations at farms.

4.2.4 Action Plan

This section sets the time plan for the deployment of the channels and activities that will be used for each of the targeted stakeholders of the Danish UC. The action plan for the stakeholders' engagement in the region is summarised in Table 8.

Table 8. Stakeholders' Engagement Action Plan for the Danish UC

Targeted stakeholder	Channel/Action	Timing
Agricultural Advisers, Energy Companies, Technology Providers, Governmental Bodies	Initial e-mail communications and personal interactions (T3.1)	M10-M12
All DK UC stakeholders	First round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M07-M18
All DK UC stakeholders	Second round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M19-M27
All DK UC stakeholders	Awareness-raising campaign (T3.2)	M15-M27
All DK UC stakeholders	Capacity building – training workshop (T3.4)	M19-M27
All DK UC stakeholders	Co-creation sessions for the definition of the weighting criteria (T6.2)	M19-M30
All DK UC stakeholders	Final co-creation sessions (T6.4)	M19-M36
All DK UC stakeholders	Use Case working groups (T2.5)	M09-M36
All DK UC stakeholders	Business model workshops (T7.2)	M31-M36
Governmental bodies, Authorities	Policy sessions (T7.3)	M13-M30

4.3 Spain – VdV

4.3.1 Current situation

The VdV-VRT use case in Spain focuses on integrating RES, specifically PV systems, with agricultural activities to promote sustainability and economic viability. Besides the common HarvREST engagement goals, the specific vision for stakeholder engagement in the VdV – VRT Use Case is to raise **awareness** and support **knowledge diffusion** on the benefits of integrating RES at the farm level. This vision will be achieved by **demonstrating** the environmental, economic, and technical **benefits** of RES to key local stakeholders; strengthening existing partnerships and reaching out to potential new allies.

The Spanish Vdv-VRT Use case is composed of these three partners as shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Composition of the Spanish VdV-VRT UC

Partner	Stakeholder group	Role in the project
Vinas del Vero (VdV)	Vineyard	Use Case
Viñedos del Rio Tajo (VRT)	Vineyard	Use Case
CIRCE	Research Centre	UC supporter RTO

4.3.2 Local Stakeholder Ecosystem

The local stakeholder ecosystem includes diverse groups with varying roles and perspectives on RES integration. **Energy companies** and **SMEs** provide technological expertise and investment in RES projects, making them crucial for the development and implementation of renewable energy solutions. **Local value chain actors, farmers, and the livestock industry** directly benefit from reduced energy costs and enhanced sustainability through RES adoption, making their involvement essential for the practical application of these technologies. **Energy communities** and **RESCoops** promote community-driven energy solutions and advocate for local energy autonomy, ensuring that the benefits of renewable energy projects are realised at the community level. **Agricultural associations and cooperatives** facilitate knowledge sharing and provide support

for integrating RES into farming practices, helping to disseminate best practices and drive widespread adoption. **Local authorities** are responsible for creating regulatory frameworks and providing policy support to enable RES deployment in agriculture, ensuring that the necessary legal and institutional conditions are in place to support renewable energy initiatives.

4.3.3 *Strategy for stakeholder engagement (per stakeholder group)*

The stakeholder groups mentioned above vary in knowledge, scale, and interest. Furthermore, each stakeholder group has different motivations and concerns towards the integration of RES at the farm level. Therefore, tailor-made messages and strategies per stakeholder group are presented below, aiming to better address their specific concerns, needs, and motivations.

Energy Companies and SMEs

The motivation of Energy Companies and SMEs to join the Spanish VdV-VRT UC activities can be triggered by showcasing the economic and social benefits of RES. The initial step of communication can be done via an **informative letter or email**, introducing HarvREST's vision and goals, as well as the activities and the goals of the Spanish Use case. This first approach will have two goals: i) provide information about RES and HarvREST's vision, and ii) invite them to join the activities of the Spanish VdV-VRT Use case.

Key Messages:

- **Economic opportunities through RES investment:**
 - Highlight the potential for profitability and growth through investments in renewable energy projects
 - Emphasis on the long-term financial benefits such as reduced operational costs and revenue from energy sales.
- **Technological innovation and market expansion:**
 - Stress the role of technological advancements in enhancing competitiveness and expanding market reach in the renewable energy sector.

Following this, this group can be further engaged through their participation in the **warm-up events (T3.1)**, **training workshops (T3.4)**, and **awareness-raising activities (T3.2)**. In the framework of the Spanish VdV UC awareness-raising campaign, **farm visits and technology demonstrations** can take place, including visits to operational RES installations to demonstrate technology capabilities, efficiency gains, and integration possibilities with agricultural activities. Additionally, **tailored newsletters on regulatory updates and project successes** can be circulated among energy companies and SME representatives, providing regular updates on regulatory changes impacting the RES sector and sharing success stories from implementing projects to build credibility and trust.

Local Value Chain Actors, Farmers, and Livestock Industry

The motivation of local value chain actors, farmers, and the livestock industry to participate in the Spanish VdV-VRT Use Case activities can be encouraged by highlighting the economic and environmental benefits of RES adoption. The initial communication can be made through an **informative letter or email**, introducing HarvREST's vision and goals, as well as the activities and objectives of the Spanish Use Case. This initial outreach will focus on i) sharing information about RES and HarvREST's vision, and ii) inviting them to take part in the

activities of the Spanish VdV-VRT Use Case, including the warm-up events (T3.1), awareness-raising activities (T3.2), and training workshops (T3.4).

Key Messages

- **Economic benefits and sustainability improvements:**
 - Highlight cost savings through reduced energy expenditures and enhanced sustainability practices, such as carbon footprint reduction and environmental stewardship.
- **Environmental stewardship through RES adoption:**
 - Emphasise the role of RES in preserving natural resources, improving air quality, and promoting sustainable land management practices.

In the context of T3.4, **peer-to-peer learning opportunities** will be facilitated among farmers and local actors to share insights, challenges, and solutions related to RES integration. These will indicatively include the practical aspects of installing, operating, and maintaining RES systems, tailored to the needs of agricultural settings. As part of the awareness-raising activities (T3.2) in Spain-VdV, **participation in local agricultural events** will be encouraged to raise awareness, educate stakeholders on RES benefits, and foster community dialogue on sustainable farming practices. During the warm-up events, networking opportunities will be provided, to namely foster **collaboration with agricultural associations to advocate for policies** that support dual land use, ensuring RES integration does not compromise agricultural productivity or land quality.

Energy Communities/RESCoops, Agricultural Associations and Cooperatives

The motivation of Energy Communities/RESCoops and agricultural associations to engage in the Spanish VdV-VRT Use Case activities can be fostered by emphasizing the community and economic advantages of RES adoption. The first step in communication can be through a detailed **letter or email**, outlining HarvREST's vision, goals, and the specific objectives of the Spanish Use Case. This initial outreach will focus on two main objectives: first, to share insights on RES and HarvREST's vision, and second, to encourage their active involvement in the Spanish VdV-VRT Use Case activities, including **the warm-up events (T3.1), awareness-raising activities (T3.2), and training workshops (T3.4)**.

Key Messages

- **Community-driven energy solutions and local resilience:**
 - Promote the benefits of community-led RES projects in enhancing local energy security, resilience to external disruptions, and fostering community cohesion.
- **Collective action and economic benefits of energy autonomy:**
 - Highlight the economic advantages of locally produced and consumed energy, such as reduced transmission losses and potential revenue from surplus energy sales.

In the context of awareness-raising activities (T3.2), a series of **newsletters** can be published to update community members on project developments, achievements, and upcoming opportunities for participation. Additionally, **community gatherings and farm visits** can be organised to discuss RES opportunities, address concerns, and gather community input on potential projects. The **training workshops** (T3.4) will provide the

opportunity for community members to gain knowledge on social, economic and technical aspects of agrivoltaics technology and the national regulatory framework.

Local Authorities, Governmental bodies

The motivation of local authorities to participate in the Spanish VdV-VRT UC activities can be enhanced by emphasising the economic growth and regulatory advantages offered by RES integration into agricultural practices in the region. The initial communication can be delivered through a well-drafted **letter or email**, presenting HarvREST's vision, goals, and the specific objectives of the Spanish UC. This outreach will target two key aims: first, to highlight the benefits of RES and HarvREST's vision, and second, to invite their active participation in the Spanish VdV-VRT Use Case activities.

Engaging local authorities in the Spanish case is crucial for advancing the project's vision. Local, regional, and national authorities can be engaged through the UC activities including **warm-up events (T3.1)**, **training workshops (T3.4)**, and **awareness-raising activities (T3.2)**. To ensure clear communication, relevant promotional materials will be provided in Spanish. Participation of project partners in external events, such as conferences, will be a key strategy for building connections and identifying synergies with broader EU initiatives. Ongoing communication, including email and phone outreach, will be used to present the outcomes of co-creation activities. Additionally, inviting these authorities to participate in **project policy sessions (T7.3)** will facilitate discussions on relevant policies and investments at both local and EU levels.

Key Messages

- **Economic development through RES integration**
 - Highlight the role of RES projects in stimulating local economic growth, creating jobs, and attracting investment in sustainable technologies.
- **Regulatory support for streamlined processes**
 - Advocate for policies that simplify administrative procedures, reduce bureaucratic barriers, and encourage investment in RES infrastructure.

4.3.4 Action Plan

Based on the Grant Agreement requirements and the needs of the Use Case, a preliminary timeline of the HarvREST stakeholder engagement strategy and plan for the Spanish UC is presented in Table 10. The implementation time plan accounts for the stakeholder engagement activities foreseen by the end of the project, and it's subject to slight adjustments as long as task durations are respected.

Table 10. Stakeholders’ engagement action plan for the Spanish VdV-VRT UC

Targeted stakeholder	Channel/Action	Timing
Energy sector & Technology providers, Academia	Initial e-mail communications and personal interactions (T3.1)	M10-M12
All ES UC stakeholders	First round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M07-M18
All ES UC stakeholders	Second round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M19-M27
All ES UC stakeholders	Awareness-raising campaign (T3.2)	M15-M27
All ES UC stakeholders	Capacity building – training workshop (T3.4)	M17-M27
All ES UC stakeholders	Co-creation sessions for the definition of the weighting criteria (T6.2)	M19-M30
All ES UC stakeholders	Final co-creation sessions (T6.4)	M19-M36
All ES UC stakeholders	Use Case working groups (T2.5)	M09-M36
All ES UC stakeholders	Business model workshops (T7.2)	M31-M36
Governmental bodies, Authorities	Policy sessions (T7.3)	M13-M30

4.4 Spain - ACSA-Sorigué

4.4.1 Current situation

ACSA-Sorigué aims to leverage Catalonia’s abundant biogenic resources to produce biogas through anaerobic digestion, aligning with circular economy principles and waste hierarchy. The agriculture and livestock sectors play a pivotal role in this process, significantly contributing to methane emissions, which can be mitigated through biogas production. The vision for stakeholder engagement in the ACSA-Sorigué UC is to create an inclusive, well-informed, and collaborative environment that promotes the integration of RES in agriculture. The core component of the stakeholder engagement strategy for this Use Case will focus on awareness and knowledge sharing. In addition to common engagement activities across all Use Cases (such as **awareness-raising campaigns** and **warm-ups**), this vision will be achieved through **knowledge-sharing** initiatives and the **active involvement of local champions**.

The Spanish ACSA-Sorigué Use Case is composed of these two partners shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Composition of the Spanish ACSA-Sorigué UC

Partner	Stakeholder group	Role in the project
Sorigué / ACSA	Company active in construction, services, technology, energy and water engineering sectors	Use Case
UVic-UCC / BETA	Research Centre	UC supporter RTO

4.4.2 Local Stakeholder Ecosystem

The key target stakeholders in ACSA-Sorigué include a diverse range of groups essential for the success of renewable energy initiatives. **Energy companies and Investors** lead the way in developing renewable energy technologies and play a crucial role in executing pilot projects, positioning them as key players in the shift towards sustainable energy. **Farmers** play a crucial role, as their participation and support directly impact the success of renewable energy projects, given their control over the land and resources needed for such initiatives. **Livestock industry representatives** are also vital, as they can drive demand for renewable energy

technologies that can be integrated into livestock operations, enhancing efficiency and sustainability. **Environmental associations** advocate for sustainable practices and support renewable energy integration, helping to validate the environmental benefits of these projects and influencing public opinion and policy. **Energy communities** are crucial for promoting decentralised energy solutions and ensuring that the economic benefits of renewable energy projects are shared locally. Finally, **public authorities** are essential for creating a supportive regulatory environment and providing the necessary incentives and infrastructure to facilitate renewable energy adoption.

4.4.3 Strategy for stakeholder engagement (per stakeholder group)

These stakeholder groups differ in their levels of knowledge, scale of operations, and interests. Additionally, each group has unique motivations and concerns regarding the integration of RES at the farm level. As a result, customised messages and strategies have been developed for each stakeholder group, with the goal of more effectively addressing their particular concerns, needs, and motivations.

Energy companies, Investors & agro-entrepreneurs

Energy companies and investors are among the most important groups for RES integration in farms in the Spanish ACSA-Sorigué UC. The UC team will trigger their interest in the project activities by presenting them with the economic and environmental benefits of RES integration, and more specifically biogas production at the farm level. CBC (Clúster Bioenergía de Catalunya) can support the engagement process with their existing links with industry actors. A starting point for engaging them in the process will be **via e-mails or one-to-one meetings**. A brief project presentation will help stakeholders become acquainted with the goals, concepts, and ideas of HarvREST and the local UC. At a later stage, Energy companies, Investors & agro-entrepreneurs will be engaged in the project activities, including the **warm-up events (T3.1)**, **training workshops (T3.4)**, and **awareness raising activities (T3.2)**.

Key Messages:

- **Economic Returns:** Emphasise the potential for high returns on investment through the integration of RES, particularly biogas production at the farm level, which can create new revenue streams and reduce operational costs.
- **Environmental Impact:** Highlight the significant role that RES can play in reducing carbon footprints and promoting sustainable agricultural practices, aligning with corporate sustainability goals and ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) criteria.
- **Market Leadership:** Position RES integration as a cutting-edge opportunity to lead in the renewable energy market, setting industry standards and capitalising on early adoption in the agricultural sector.

Farmers, Livestock industry representatives

Farmers are one of the leading stakeholder groups of the Spanish ACSA-Sorigué UC, as well as Livestock industry representatives. A key motivation for engagement will be presenting them the economic benefits of biogas facilities at farms, and explaining in simple terms the technicalities and current legislative frameworks in place. The project activities, **warm-up events (T3.1)**, **training workshops (T3.4)**, and **awareness raising activities (T3.2)** will facilitate their exchanges with technical experts, and their participation in community

meetings and industry events to share their experiences and challenges and improve their understanding of the benefits of RES.

Key Messages:

- **Economic benefits of biogas production:** Highlight the potential cost savings and additional revenue streams from biogas generation and digestate as organic fertilisers.
- **Environmental sustainability and methane emission reduction:** Emphasise how biogas production reduces methane emissions from organic waste, contributing to environmental stewardship.
- **Integration of biogas as a sustainable waste management solution:** Highlight the role of biogas in reducing waste and lowering environmental impact.
- **Economic incentives through biogas valorisation:** Discuss the economic benefits of biogas production and the potential for revenue generation from biogas projects.
- **Improvements in agriculture through digestate use:** Emphasise the benefits of using digestate as a high-quality organic fertiliser, improving soil health, boosting crop yields, and reducing the need for synthetic fertilisers, further enhancing farm sustainability.

The initial phase of communication with farmers will involve informing them about the project, its overall methodology, and the specific objectives of the Spanish UC through personal interactions and emails. Project promotional materials and communication channels, including **newsletters, press releases, social media, and the website**, will be utilised for this purpose.

In the context of the UC **awareness-raising campaign** (T3.2), **farm visits and demonstration events** can be organised, where examples of successful biogas facilities' implementation will be showcased. By seeing the technology in action, farmers and livestock industry representatives can better understand how biogas can be integrated into their own operations, reducing perceived risks and uncertainties. During **the training workshops** (T3.4), farmers and livestock industry representatives will learn about the technical aspects of biogas production, such as system maintenance, methane capture, and waste management. These sessions could also cover the current legislative frameworks and economic incentives available.

During the warm-up events, farmers will be given the opportunity to **connect with peers** who have already adopted biogas technology. These events can include panel discussions, roundtable meetings, or informal **networking sessions**. These events will allow stakeholders to share their experiences, discuss challenges, and explore solutions collaboratively, thereby enhancing their confidence in adopting biogas technologies.

These events will help identify potential early adopters and local champions who can further advocate for the HarvRESt approach. Engagement will be strengthened by involving farmers in the co-design of tools and solutions, offering them direct benefits and incentives for participating in HarvRESt activities.

Environmental Associations, Energy Communities

A key motivation for Environmental Associations to engage in the Spanish UC activities is the opportunity to learn about the socioeconomic and environmental benefits of biogas production at farms, particularly given their previous resistance to such projects. By joining the UC activities, Environmental Associations can play a crucial role in shaping its environmental practices, ensuring that biogas production is implemented in an environmentally responsible manner. Their involvement can help advocate for higher environmental standards and influence public policy towards more sustainable farming practices. At the same time, Energy

Communities/RESCoops are driven by the desire to increase local control over energy production and consumption. The UC's focus on biogas production at farms offers a way to generate renewable energy locally, reducing reliance on external energy sources and promoting energy independence within the community. By participating in the UC activities, Energy Communities can ensure that the economic gains from biogas production stay within the local area, supporting local development and sustainability.

Key Messages:

- **Transparency in biogas operations and environmental impacts:** Emphasise the importance of environmental monitoring and reporting in biogas projects.
- **Collaboration opportunities for sustainable development:** Advocate for sustainable biogas practices and policies that align with environmental conservation goals.
- **Renewable energy benefits of biogas:** Highlight the role of biogas in diversifying energy sources and reducing dependence on fossil fuels.
- **Collective action for energy independence:** Promote community-based biogas projects that empower local energy communities.

In the framework of the **awareness-raising activities (T3.2)**, **farm visits and stories of collective action** that have demonstrated significant social and environmental impacts on local communities can inspire environmental associations and energy communities. Additionally, as part of T3.2 activities, **workshops focused on environmental transparency can be organised**, showcasing how biogas production can be properly monitored and reported responsibly. These workshops can invite environmental associations to actively participate in designing and overseeing the environmental monitoring processes.

Public Authorities

Public authorities' motivation to join HarvRESt activities can be triggered through economical aspects as well as through social benefits. Biogas production at farms can stimulate local economies by creating jobs, generating new revenue streams, and attracting investments in rural areas. Public Authorities, particularly at the local and regional levels, would be motivated by the potential to boost economic activity, support agricultural sustainability, and enhance energy security. Their participation can help in designing incentive structures, subsidies, and other financial mechanisms to encourage widespread adoption. Their endorsement and involvement in the **warm-up events (T3.1)** can legitimise the project, making it more likely to gain public support. Communication can take place either through email or phone and further interaction through invitations to the project workshops, policy events is foreseen.

Key Messages:

- **Policy support for renewable energy integration:** Highlight the role of biogas in achieving regional and national renewable energy targets.
- **Economic and environmental benefits of biogas projects:** Emphasise the potential for job creation, economic growth, and greenhouse gas emissions reduction through biogas.

In the context of the **awareness-raising campaign (T3.2)**, visits to **success cases** can take place to demonstrate how supportive policies have enabled these successes. Authorities gain a clearer understanding of the real-world impact of their policies, facilitating informed decision-making. In the same context, public authorities

will be encouraged to participate in public information campaigns that explain the benefits of biogas, the role of local governance, and how supportive policies can encourage more farms to adopt renewable energy. As part of the UC **policy sessions** (T7.3), public authorities can participate in roundtable discussions that bring together local, regional, and national authorities to discuss the role of biogas in regional development and how policy can support its integration.

4.4.4 Action Plan

This section sets the time plan for the deployment of the channels and activities that will be used for each of the targeted stakeholders of the Spanish ACSA-Sorigué UC. The action plan for the stakeholders' engagement in the region is summarised in Table 12.

Table 12. Stakeholders' engagement action plan for the Spanish ACSA-Sorigué UC

Targeted stakeholder	Channel/Action	Timing
Energy sector & Technology providers, Academia	Initial e-mail communications and personal interactions (T3.1)	M10-M12
All ES UC stakeholders	First round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M07-M18
All ES UC stakeholders	Second round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M19-M27
All ES UC stakeholders	Awareness-raising campaign (T3.2)	M15-M27
All ES UC stakeholders	Capacity building – training workshop (T3.4)	M17-M27
All ES UC stakeholders	Co-creation sessions for the definition of the weighting criteria (T6.2)	M19-M30
All ES UC stakeholders	Final co-creation sessions (T6.4)	M19-M36
All ES UC stakeholders	Use Case working groups (T2.5)	M09-M36
All ES UC stakeholders	Business model workshops (T7.2)	M31-M36
Authorities, Policymakers	Policy sessions (T7.3)	M13-M30

4.5 Norway – GGE

4.5.1 Current situation

In Norway, GGE will install wind and hydropower technologies to achieve 100% renewable energy coverage. Currently, GGE meets 50% of their energy demand with existing assets, requiring effective integration with new installations through smart energy systems. GGE and NORCE will collaborate to develop an intelligent energy system for total decarbonisation, focusing on data management for optimised asset coordination. The key objective is to manage energy storage interaction with renewable assets and optimise resource use in farm activities. Additionally, GGE will explore synergies with the Spanish-ACSA-Sorigué and the Danish UCs for biogas production and Combined Heat and Power (CHP) installations, aiming for broader technology deployment and replication.

The engagement vision focuses on demonstrating the feasibility and benefits of utilising the local potential of renewable energy systems around the UC. By prioritising education, awareness campaigns, and robust knowledge sharing, the goal is to pave the way for broader adoption and dissemination of RES technologies in the agricultural sector.

The Norwegian Use case is composed of these two partners shown in Table 13.

Table 13. Composition of the Norwegian UC

Partner	Stakeholder group	Role in the project
Grønn Gårdsenergi (GGE)	Farm (cattle, sheep and pigs)	Use Case
Norwegian Research Centre (NORCE)	Research Institute	UC Supporter RTO

4.5.2 Local Stakeholder Ecosystem

The Norwegian UC involves a diverse and interconnected local stakeholder ecosystem, crucial for the successful integration of RES in the agricultural sector. The **energy companies** and **technology providers** play a vital role in supplying and maintaining the necessary RES infrastructure. The involvement of **Individual researchers and research organisations** ensures continuous innovation and the dissemination of best practices. Additionally, **Authorities** and **national ministries** are instrumental in creating a conducive regulatory environment and facilitating funding opportunities for RES adoption. **Clusters & Sectorial organisations** contribute by raising awareness, supporting farmers, and raising public support for RES initiatives. Together, these stakeholders form a collaborative network aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable energy practices within the agricultural landscape of Norway.

4.5.3 Strategy for stakeholder engagement (per stakeholder group)

Each stakeholder group has unique motivations and concerns regarding the integration of RE solutions at the farm level. Therefore, customised messages and strategies have been developed for each stakeholder group, designed to more effectively address their specific concerns, needs, and motivations.

Energy Companies and SMEs

Energy companies and SMEs are among the most important groups for RES integration in farms in the Norwegian UC. The UC partners will trigger their interest in the project activities by presenting them with the economic and environmental benefits of RES integration at the farm level. A starting point for engaging them in the process will be via e-mails, direct and personal discussions and meetings. A short project presentation will help to familiarise stakeholders with the goals, concepts, and ideas of HarvREST and the local UC. At a later stage, Energy companies and SMEs will be engaged in the project activities, including the **training workshops (T3.4)**, **warm-up events (T3.1)**, and **awareness-raising activities (T3.2)**.

Key Messages

Economic opportunities through RES investment

- **Profitability through Innovation:** Detail the financial incentives and business growth opportunities presented by investing in RES, including access to new markets and diversified energy portfolios.
- **Cost Efficiency:** Demonstrate how RES can lower operational costs and improve profit margins through efficient energy use and the potential sale of excess energy.
- **Government Incentives:** Highlight available government subsidies, tax breaks, and financial incentives for RES investments, making the case for RES as a financially viable venture.

In the Norwegian UC, this group can be further engaged through participation in **warm-up events (T3.1)**, **training workshops (T3.4)**, and **awareness-raising activities (T3.2)**. As part of the Norwegian UC awareness campaign, **farm visits and technology demonstrations** can be organised, including tours of operational RES

installations to showcase technology capabilities, efficiency improvements, and the potential for integration with agricultural activities. Additionally, **tailored newsletters** focusing on regulatory updates and project successes can be distributed to energy companies and SMEs representatives, providing them with regular insights into regulatory changes affecting the RES sector and sharing success stories from completed projects to build credibility and foster trust.

Individual Researchers, Research organisations

The engagement of Individual Researchers and Research organisations is important for the creation of synergies and involvement of researchers and students in fostering RES uptake at farms. They can foster education and training through STEM methodologies to familiarise the general public with the potential and benefits of RES applications at farms. The first communication can take place either through email or phone to inform them about the overall approach of HarvRESt as well as the specific scope of the Norwegian UC.

Key Messages:

- Emphasise the role of research and innovation in advancing RES technologies for agriculture.
- Highlight the importance of academic-industry partnerships in driving practical, real-world solutions.

Inviting researchers to participate in the project's **warm-up events (T3.1), awareness-raising activities (T3.2), and training workshops (T3.4)** will allow them to contribute their expertise while gaining insights into the project's progress and outcomes. Such involvement can also inspire new research directions and foster the integration of STEM education methodologies to promote RES understanding among the broader public.

As part of the warm-up events (T3.1), researchers will be provided with **networking opportunities** and the chance to **establish partnerships** with other universities and research institutions. These connections can also facilitate access to grants and funding opportunities specifically aimed at RES innovation in agriculture.

Clusters & Sectorial organisations

Clusters and sectorial organisations can be effectively engaged in the Norwegian case of the HarvRESt project by leveraging their role as industry leaders and knowledge hubs. The UC will create opportunities for them to engage in discussions, share insights, and explore RES integration in agriculture through targeted workshops and discussions.

Key Messages:

- Promote the role of RES in achieving regional sustainability targets and enhancing farm productivity.
- Outline the technical support and resources available to farmers for RES implementation.

The first step of communication with clusters and sectorial organisations will be to inform them about the overall approach of HarvRESt as well as the specific scope of the Norwegian UC via direct **personal contact**. The promotional material of the project and the dissemination channels of the project (website, social media accounts, newsletters etc.) can be used. Following this, they will be shared invitations to join the **warm-up events (T3.1), awareness-raising activities (T3.2) and training workshops (T3.4)**.

As part of the **policy sessions (7.3)** the clusters and sectorial organisations can be further engaged to discuss policy, regulatory frameworks, and industry standards related to RES in agriculture. Additionally, in the context

of the UC awareness-raising activities, they can participate in farm visits/demonstration events where they can see **demonstrations of RES technologies on farms**. These events will provide hands-on experience and a tangible understanding of how RES can be integrated into agricultural practices, encouraging them to advocate for wider adoption within their networks.

Authorities (regional, local), National ministries

The motivation of local authorities to participate in the Norwegian Use Case activities can be boosted by highlighting the economic benefits and regulatory advantages offered by RES integration into agricultural practices in the region. The initial communication can be delivered through a well-drafted **email or direct personal contact**, presenting HarvREST's vision, goals, and the specific objectives of the Norwegian UC. This outreach will target two key aims: first, to highlight the benefits of RES and HarvREST's vision, and second, to invite their active participation in the Norwegian UC activities including the **warm-up events (T3.1), awareness raising activities (T3.2) and training workshops (T3.4)**.

Key Messages

- **Job Creation:** Emphasise how RES projects can create new jobs in installation, maintenance, and operation, boosting local economies and providing skilled employment opportunities.
- **Economic Growth:** Illustrate how RES can drive economic growth by attracting investment, fostering innovation, and enhancing competitiveness in the global market.
- **Infrastructure Development:** Explain how RES projects can lead to improvements in local infrastructure, such as upgraded energy grids and increased energy reliability.
- **Policy Alignment:** Advocate for the alignment of local policies with EU directives to ensure cohesive and supportive regulatory environments for RES adoption.
- **Streamlined Approvals:** Stress the importance of simplifying administrative procedures to expedite RES project approvals and reduce bureaucratic hurdles.
- **Incentives and Support:** Encourage the development of supportive policies, including grants, subsidies, and technical assistance programs, to promote RES adoption and address potential barriers.

In the framework of the policy activities, the authorities and ministries' representatives can be further engaged in policy discussions during the HarvREST **policy sessions (T7.3)**, where they can directly engage with project leaders and other stakeholders to discuss and shape the regulatory frameworks that support RES integration. Additionally, in the context of the Norwegian UC awareness-raising campaign (T3.2), **site visits to operational RES installations at farms** can take place, providing a practical understanding of the benefits and feasibility of these technologies, demonstrating how they align with regional development goals such as job creation, economic growth, and infrastructure development. These visits can be coupled with presentations on the long-term economic benefits and potential job creation associated with RES projects, tailored to resonate with the authorities' mandates and interests.

4.5.4 Action Plan

This section sets the time plan for the deployment of the channels and activities that will be used for each of the targeted stakeholders of the Norwegian UC. The action plan for the stakeholders' engagement in the region is summarised in Table 14.

Table 14. Stakeholders' engagement action plan for the Norwegian UC

Targeted stakeholder	Channel/Action	Timing
All NO UC stakeholders	Initial e-mail communications and personal interactions (T3.1)	M10-M12
All NO UC stakeholders	First round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M07-M18
All NO UC stakeholders	Second round of warm-up events (T3.1)	M19-M27
All NO UC stakeholders	Awareness-raising campaign (T3.2)	M15-M27
All NO UC stakeholders	Capacity building – training workshop (T3.4)	M19-M27
All NO UC stakeholders	Co-creation sessions for the definition of the weighting criteria (T6.2)	M19-M30
All NO UC stakeholders	Final co-creation sessions (T6.4)	M19-M36
All NO UC stakeholders	Use Case working groups (T2.5)	M09-M36
All NO UC stakeholders	Business model workshops (T7.2)	M31-M36
All NO UC stakeholders	Policy sessions (T7.3)	M13-M30

5. CONCLUSIONS, MONITORING AND NEXT STEPS

The HarvRESt stakeholders’ engagement approach will be results-driven in order to facilitate the dynamic nature of a stakeholders’ engagement strategy. In particular, in close collaboration with the UCs, we might need to streamline our process, after identifying issues such as unexpected difficulties during the engagement of stakeholders, identification of new and important key stakeholders, challenges in stakeholders’ commitment due to inappropriate selection of channels, etc. To this end, the UC-based strategies for stakeholder engagement will be closely monitored in order to ensure the optimal deployment as well as the effectiveness of the applied actions. This monitoring framework will enable the deployment of mitigation actions in case of low engagement levels and will, thus, significantly assist HarvRESt in meeting the engagement objectives and targets that have been set.

For this reason, the Stakeholder mapping template (Annex 7.1) has been created and uploaded on the projects’ SharePoint to be accessible and editable in real time by all the relevant partners.

The effectiveness of the monitoring framework will be continuously monitored (Table 15) and adaptations will be made as/if required. The engagement process is dynamic and the actions described above will be continuously monitored and modified or complemented if deemed appropriate. The evolution and results of the stakeholder engagement activities will be reported in D3.5 HarvRESt strategy for multi-actor engagement and awareness creation in agro communities (final version) – M30.

Table 15. Measures for Monitoring the stakeholders’ Engagement Strategies’ effectiveness

Activity	Metric	Target
Warm-up events (T3.1)	Number of events	2 per Use Case/ 10 in total
Training workshops (T3.4)	Number of activities and stakeholders involved	1 per Use Case/ min 10 participants
Awareness Raising Campaigns (T3.2)	Number of activities and stakeholders involved	No direct number set at the Grant Agreement level

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Koopmans, M. et al. (2018) 'The role of multi-actor governance in aligning farm modernization and sustainable rural development', *Journal of Rural Studies*, 59, pp. 252–262. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2017.03.012>.
- [2] Calliera, M. et al. (2021) 'Multi-actor approach and engagement strategy to promote the adoption of best management practices and a sustainable use of pesticides for groundwater quality improvement in hilly vineyards', *Science of The Total Environment*, 752, p. 142251. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142251>.
- [3] Guerrero-Ocampo, S.B., Díaz-Puente, J.M. and Nuñez Espinoza, J.F. (2022) 'Multi-Actor Partnerships for Agricultural Interactive Innovation: Findings from 17 Case Studies in Europe', *Land*, 11(10), p. 1847. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11101847>.

7. ANNEXES

7.1 Stakeholder groups identification template

Instructions: Please examine the existing list of stakeholder groups and subgroups. For each stakeholder sub-group, carefully indicate each of the dimensions specified in the table. You can use the drop-down menu to define the current/desired level of engagement, the influence, and the impact. For channels of communication and extra remarks, insert text. You are most welcome to identify a new stakeholder group and/or subgroup. In this case, please include your addition(s) in the respective fields. You can find a small glossary with definitions at the bottom of this sheet.

Stakeholder Group	Stakeholder Subgroup	Current level of engagement	Desired level of engagement	Influence	Impact	Channels of communication	Comments
G1: Industry	Energy sector companies						
	Transport companies						
	Investors & agro-entrepreneurs						
	SMEs and micro-enterprises						
	Technology providers						
	Medium and large-sized energy industries						
	Primary producers, energy end users						
G2: Agri-sector	Agriculture machinery private sector						
	Local value chain actors						
	Farmers						
G3: Academia and scientific community	Livestock Industry Representatives						
	Individual researchers						
	Research organisations						
	R&D units in private companies						
G4: Civil society	Universities						
	General public						
	Citizen associations						

	NGOs					
	Civil Society Associations					
	Environmental Associations					
	Energy communities/RESCoops					
	Agricultural Associations/cooperatives					
	Clusters & Sectorial organisations					
	<i>[Add new subgroup here]</i>					
G5: Policy makers	Regional authorities					
	Local authorities (e.g. municipalities)					
	National ministries					
	National / EU agencies					
	Parties / Parliament Advisors / European Associations					
	Agricultural Sustainability Advocates					
	<i>[Add new subgroup here]</i>					
Other	1.500 Climate Pilot Farms					
	Research projects					
	Regional/local media outlets					
	EU-funded initiatives					
	<i>[Add new subgroup here]</i>					

Instructions: As part of cooperation with T2.3/T2.5 and as a horizontal effort to gather a pool of relevant stakeholders for HarvRESt activities, here you can indicate individuals that might be of interest for the project. Please, provide around 13-15 stakeholders in total. Only include stakeholders whose information is available online.

HarvRESt Stakeholder groups identification template

	<i>Dropdown</i>	<i>Dropdown</i>	<i>Please fill in</i>	<i>Dropdown</i>	<i>Dropdown</i>	<i>Please fill in</i>	<i>Dropdown</i>	<i>Dropdown</i>	<i>Please fill in (Name, role, email or other contact information)</i>	<i>If necessary, provide any additional comment</i>
No.	HarvRESt Partner name	Region involved	Stakeholder name	Stakeholder group	Stakeholder subgroup	Channel of communication	Influence	Impact	Contact	Comments (including potential stakeholder's contribution, related expertise, etc).
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	
									-	

7.2 Warm-up events - Guidelines

7.2.1 Task description

According to the Grant Agreement (GA), a key step for stakeholder engagement in HarvREST involves organising warm-up events to introduce the project in the local Use Cases. Following the GA, **at least two warm-up events/actions shall be organised by local partners in each Use Case.**

In this context, the local Use Case partners, supported by their RTOs, are responsible for organising these events, following the guidelines shared by White Research. Once the event has taken place, the local Use Case partners are required to fill in the reporting template described in this document.

Both rounds of warm-up events will bring a broader part of the target community together to promote knowledge sharing and exchange on good practices (WP2 insights) as well as to promote networking, initiating or reinforcing existing collaborations and synergies.

7.2.2 Warm-up objectives

These events should be dynamic and diverse to fit the various regional settings of the Use Cases. They will lay a solid foundation for subsequent project activities (such as the awareness-raising campaigns under T3.2), ensuring a cohesive and impactful stakeholder engagement process. The overall objectives of the warm-up actions are:

Introduce the Project in Local Use Case areas:

- Provide a comprehensive introduction to the HarvREST project tailored to local contexts (in the local language).
- Ensure that stakeholders in each Use case are well-informed about the project's aims and activities. Both overall HarvREST objectives and Use Case specific objectives should be included.

Foster Stakeholder Engagement:

- Attract further mobilisation of the local actors
- Actively engage local stakeholders to build a strong, involved community.
- Facilitate meaningful interactions and collaborations between different stakeholders.

Promote Knowledge Sharing and Exchange:

- Disseminate best practices and insights from Work Package 2 (WP2), key findings on main challenges, and opportunities at the local level.
- Create a platform for sharing experiences and knowledge that can benefit all participants.
- Set the basis for the Awareness-raising campaigns.

Promote Networking:

- Initiate or reinforce existing collaborations and synergies.
- Encourage networking to support the development of new relationships and the strengthening of existing ones.

It should be clear that these objectives frame the overarching purpose of these actions. It is expected that Use Case partners and their RTOs clearly define specific pilot objectives for each warm-up.

Please note:

The **first round of warm-up events** will mainly focus on engaging local stakeholders, introducing them to the project and its vision and collecting feedback from the local community to better steer the project and align it with regional needs.

The **second round** will be enhanced with the presentation of some key project results and further engagement in fruitful discussions. Ideally, the second round will take place once the project has generated some initial results to update the stakeholders involved about HarvREST’s progress.

7.2.3 Action plan for the warm-up events

Action	Who	When
Initial guidelines and template	White	Early June 2024 (M6)
Share event plan and agenda (4 – 6 weeks before each event)	Use Case & RTO	M7 – M18 (1 st Round) M18 – M27 (2 nd Round)
Event organisation and implementation phase	Use Case & RTO	M7 – M18 (1 st Round) M18 – M27 (2 nd Round)
Fill out workshop reporting templates and send them to WR	Use Case & RTO	Max 2 weeks after the warm-up
Analysis of the warm-up actions outcomes	White	TBD

7.2.4 Before the event

There are several steps that need to be followed to organise a warm-up event. Before holding the warm-up, all Use Cases and their RTOs should:

- **Define a diverse audience.** - The main goal of the warm-up events is to promote HarvREST's vision and attract further mobilisation of local actors, bringing a broader part of the community together. To achieve that purpose, identify a broad set of relevant local stakeholders to invite, including citizens, public authorities, farmers, energy cooperatives, agricultural associations, medium and large-sized energy industries, etc. More information on this is provided in Section 3.2.
- **Pick a date, a venue, and a suitable time.** - Adapt to your audience. It is better to avoid work hours and local holidays. The duration of the event might vary, but it should not exceed 2-3 hours, especially if held online, to maintain the attendees’ interest. Please, take into consideration that invitations should be sent, ideally, at least 6 weeks before the warm-up event date.
- **Prepare an invitation email, an online registration form, and make sure that participants sign Consent Form before joining:** Once you have identified participants and fixed a date, invitations can be sent. Please note that tailored invitations are more effective than generic emails. Do not forget to include a registration form in the email. As the warn-up events need to be reported, it is important to know

how many participants have attended per stakeholder group and subgroup. For the Consent Form, please see Subsection 7.2.12.

- **Select digital platform** (if online): choose the software that will be used based on the specific needs of the events. For example, if you want to have brainstorming or co-creation sessions, platforms that support the formation and management of rooms are preferable. More information on this is provided in Section 3.2.
- **Prepare the event communication text and identify key hashtags:** use simple language and hashtags to be used in the dissemination of the event across social media channels, email, etc.
- **Send out communication text two weeks before the event:** proper dissemination can result in higher rates of attendance and thus, higher rates of holding a successful event.
- **Inform the HarvREST dissemination and communication manager** (FBCD) and the consortium: exploit the existing channels of the project to disseminate your event. On top of this, you may also use the channels of organisations your Use Case has already been working with.
- **Assign roles of facilitator and support coordinator:** the events need to have at least one facilitator, who will lead the event, and one support coordinator, who may take notes, support external programs and collect answers for Q&A. Notetaking is crucial for the development of further project activities, so the person dedicated to taking notes should be exempted of other tasks. If the event attracts more than 30-40 attendees or you would like to slip participants into groups, you might need more support coordinators.
- **Prepare slides for presentation (if applicable).** - This might be an introductory presentation of the project and the local Use Cases, a brief description regarding the purpose of the event and how this can be beneficial for the stakeholders. Additional information can be provided based on the specific objectives of each event.
- **Send reminders one week and the day before the event.** - based on the registration information, send a reminder to the potential attendees the day before the event to remind stakeholders of the importance of their participation.

7.2.5 *Ideas for types of events*

Different engagement formats and tools are a critical part of stakeholder engagement activities such as the HarvREST warm-up events. Not all engagement formats serve the same purpose, and they need to be selected considering not only the overall objectives for the warm-ups but each Use case's particularities and objectives. Furthermore, these tools and engagement methods must always be tailored to the specific needs of the different stakeholder groups. A non-exhaustive selection of engagement tools and formats is presented below:

- **Stakeholder workshops.** - A workshop has the advantage of convening a broad array of stakeholders to discuss various topics or prospective issues, exchange knowledge and ideas, and potentially identify or co-create solutions. For the warm-ups, some examples of topics for these workshops could be offering sessions on sustainable farming practices and integrating RES into agricultural operations.
- **Focus groups.** - Gathering a small group of stakeholders to discuss a specific topic or issue in depth can provide valuable insights into stakeholder perspectives, concerns, and preferences. This format can be particularly useful for engaging local communities.

- **Field visits or guided farm tours:** Provide tours of the Use Case farms or local farms already utilising RES to offer firsthand experiences and inspiration.
- **Community Forums:** Host panel discussions involving experts, farmers, industry representatives and residents to address concerns and promote dialogue.
- **Guest Speakers:** Invite local farmers who have successfully implemented renewable energy solutions to share their experiences and insights through short talks or Q&A sessions.
- **Networking Sessions:** Facilitate opportunities for farmers and residents to connect, share ideas, and collaborate on RES initiatives.
- **Educational Exhibits or Interventions:** Set up informational booths highlighting the benefits and practical applications of RES in farming.
- **Renewable Energy Showcases:** Host showcases featuring innovative RES technologies and success stories from other regions.
- **Information Sessions:** Schedule short, informative talks or Q&A sessions on topics like the benefits of RES for farms, financial incentives, and case studies of successful implementations.

7.2.6 Audience of warm-up events

Identify stakeholders

Participants representing varying types of stakeholders are the most important factor for the success of these events. Based on the [stakeholder identification activity](#) conducted as part of Task 3.1, the HarvREST Use Cases' ecosystem usually comprises the stakeholder groups showed in Table 16.

Table 16. Types of potential participants

Stakeholder group	Who
Industry	Energy sector companies
	Transport companies
	Investors & agro-entrepreneurs
	SMEs and micro-enterprises
	Technology providers
	Medium and large-sized energy industries
	Primary producers, energy end users
Agri-sector	Local value chain actors
	Farmers
	Livestock Industry Representatives
Academia and scientific community	Individual researchers
	Research organisations
	R&D units in private companies
	Universities
Civil society	General public
	Citizen associations
	NGOs
	Civil Society Associations
	Environmental Associations
	Energy communities/RESCoops
	Agricultural Associations/cooperatives
	Clusters & Sectorial organisations
Policymakers	Regional authorities
	Local authorities (e.g. municipalities)
	National ministries
	National / EU agencies
	Parties / Parliament Advisors / European Associations
	Agricultural Sustainability Advocates
Other	1.500 Climate Pilot Farms
	Research projects
	Regional/local media outlets
	EU-funded initiatives

Please note:

We encourage Use Cases to include participants from their working groups (T2.5) and to consult with their RTOs and UC Working group leader.

7.2.7 *Invitation Criteria*

Criteria for selecting participants:

- **Motivation:** It is crucial that the stakeholders are interested in participating in our warm-up events. Bored and indifferent participants will not be interested in further being engaged in the project's activities or disseminating the project's results at the local level.
- **Influence:** Participants with the power or capacity to make or influence decisions and affect the current framework conditions for RES integration at the farm level. For example, local or regional authorities.
- **Wide range of participants' sample:** try to cover as many stakeholder groups as possible (see Table 1) to maximise the outreach of the warm-up event and gather different perspectives.
- **Relevance for the Use Case.** – not all stakeholder groups and subgroups are the same for the different Use Cases. Some groups might not be available or present.
- **Gender balance and age:** as much as possible, warm-ups should ideally have a 50/50 distribution between female and male participants. Age may also be taken into consideration.

7.2.8 *Invitation process*

At least 2 warm-up events should take place in each Use Case, attracting 25-30 attendees per event. This number is indicative, and Pilots are encouraged to invite more participants if they wish to do so.

As detailed in the previous section, the first step is to identify potential participants via desk research or by tapping into your organisation's contact network. It is also recommended to further identify stakeholders by disseminating the event through the involved partners' social media accounts/websites, radio, or posters. Maximum advantage should also be taken of the HarvREST online presence in social networks. The project's dissemination manager (FBCD) could provide valuable advice in this regard.

After identifying potential participants, invitations can be sent to stakeholders (e.g. email invitations). It is recommended that you also attach the event agenda. Do not forget that participants must fill out an Informed Consent Form before taking part in your event (see section GDPR – Informed Consent Form).

Please, take into consideration that invitations should be sent, ideally, at least 6 weeks before the warm-up event date.

7.2.9 *Physical/Virtual Location*

In case there is difficulty in organising a physical event, organising a virtual warm-up event is a good alternative. In this context, online platforms could be used along with e-tools. Indicative suggestions, together with reference links are provided below (Table 18 and Table 19).

Table 17. Suggested Platforms

Platform	Link
Microsoft Teams	https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/microsoft-teams/group-chat-software
Zoom	https://zoom.us/
Google Hangouts	https://hangouts.google.com/
Webex	https://www.webex.com/
Slack	https://slack.com/intl/en-gr/

Table 18. Suggested e-tools

E-tools	Description	Link
Miro	Online collaborative whiteboarding, a library of templates, integration with web apps, good for brainstorming, sticky notes, freeform pen, shapes, arrows etc.	https://miro.com/
Mural	Sticky notes, text, shapes and connectors, icons, frameworks, images, gifs, Drawing	https://www.mural.co/
Google slides or Google docs	Sharing Presentations and documents	https://workspace.google.com/intl/en_ie/
Zoom built-in whiteboard	Sharing a whiteboard via Zoom	https://zoom.us/

7.2.10 Holding the event

Once the Use Cases have defined their specific goals (on top of the common objectives fully detailed in section 1.2), the next step is to have a clear overview of the warm-up structure. This one must reflect the general objectives and the specific goals set by each Use Case. Overall, each warm-up must:

- Introduce HarvREST’s vision, best practices³, and goals to the local communities
- Attract further mobilisation of the local actors and promote networking
- Foster participatory stakeholder engagement and create spaces for knowledge exchange and sharing

The structure of the event can take multiple shapes. Below, you can find two **indicative** options of how to structure the warm-up. The amount of time dedicated to each part of the event and its format are ultimately decided by each Use Case team.

³ If the Warm-up is held after D2.1 or if some of the results of this, or any other relevant open Deliverable, are available by the moment the event happens.

Option A (designed for on-site participation)

Event structure	Time	Description
Introduction*	15'	The facilitator introduces himself/herself and the team, gives an overview of the event structure, and presents the HarvRESt project.
Pilot Overview	10'	The facilitator introduces the Pilot, its goals, the technologies present, and proceeds to the upcoming tour/visit.
Fieldwork/Use Case tour	60'	The visit must trigger participants' interest, initiate the discussion around the benefits of integrating RES, and address factors that hinder or support RES uptake at the farm level.
Core session	35'	Discussion, Q&A <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brainstorming session (indicative list of questions: Brainstorming material ideas)
Closing session	10'	Wrap up and promote upcoming activities, including the second round of warm-up events.

Option B (designed both for on-site or online participation)

Event structure	Time	Description
Introduction*	15'	The facilitator introduces himself/herself, gives an overview of the event structure and introduces the HarvRESt project.
Core session Part 1	30-40'	Introduce the WP2 ⁴ or other relevant project findings. This will be done to initiate the discussion around defining regional challenges: to provide a set of aspects that hinder or support RES uptake at the farm level.
Core session Part 2	35-45'	Discussion, Q&A <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brainstorming session (indicative list of questions: Brainstorming material ideas) - If an online event, encouraged to use collaborative online tools (Miro, Zoom whiteboard etc.). If using Zoom, Meet or Teams, there's the possibility of having break-out rooms and having people assigned to them automatically or manually. If this tool is being used, you can then divide the group into smaller groups and motivate discussion by defining topics or posing specific questions.
Closing session	10'	Wrap up and promote upcoming activities, if applicable.

**In case it takes place physically, it's important to start the event with a registration process and offer them the opportunity for informal networking over coffee.*

⁴ Best practices described by Climate CKIC in D2.1

It is important to note that both options can be integrated and combined if the Use Case team has the resources to do. Finally, please remember that these are suggestions and there are multiple ways to structure and organise the warm-up event according to your Use Case needs.

7.2.11 After the event – Reporting Template

After the end of each event, the organisers should fill in the **event reporting template** (also shared via e-mail and uploaded in the SharePoint repository) and send it to WR. You can also find the template via on Teams.

7.2.12 GDPR – Informed Consent Form

Important! During the workshops' implementation, personal data (e.g. contact details, group photos or call screenshots) will be collected. **It is essential that all project activities fully comply with GDPR.**

To this aim, an **informed consent form** (GDPR – Informed consent form) should be distributed and signed by all participants before the event officially begins.

- In the case of physical events, such a form should be signed by each participant.
- In the case of virtual events, an online consent form should be prepared by organisers and filled in by participants before the workshop takes place.

For further guidance, please consult the project coordination and the WP11-related material.

After the event participants have agreed to the terms and conditions in our consent form, it is advisable to take some pictures (or screenshots in case of a virtual meeting) of your whiteboards, and post them or of your participants' brainstorming phase.

Please forward this content to the HarvREST Dissemination Manager (FBCD) and Project Coordinator (CIRCE) so that these events are properly highlighted. You could also post these pictures on your organisation's social media. Once again, it is imperative that you first get the approval/consent of all your event's attendees.

GDPR – Informed consent form⁵

Partner:

Organisation name: <Insert Partner Name>

Address: <Insert Partner Address>

Phone: <Insert Partner Phone>

Email: <Insert Partner Generic e-mail Address>

Who we are?

HarvREST is a European Project (GA 101136904) that aims to integrate Renewable Energy Systems (RES) in farms looking for synergies between the energy and food sectors. By this approach, farms will become climate neutral, optimising their production and reducing their impact on natural resources and biodiversity, on top of providing energy services to communities and diversifying their economic income. For that, HarvREST will develop an Agricultural Virtual Power Plant able to run different scenarios and farm configurations to determine the best operation procedures for a given RES solution. The full approach of HarvREST will be

⁵ The informed consent form will be shared also as a separate document with the partners involved.

supported and executed at 4 Use Cases representing different topologies of farms, a diversity of stakeholders and organisational structures, distinct geographical conditions and a wide variety of RES technologies.

What do we need from you?

You have been invited to take part in this warm-up event, **voluntarily**, because you have been identified as a key stakeholder for HarvRESt. In this context, we would like to learn more about your views on RES integration at the farm level to understand what framework conditions might act as a barrier or an enabler for the up-taking of RES.

If you decide to participate in this HarvRESt activity, we will ask you to sign a HarvRESt Informed Consent Form (provided at the end of this document) to collect and process your data. The project will last 36 months but your involvement would only be for as long as you wish.

What will we do with your data?

The information you will provide will be confidential and anonymous. HarvRESt project will handle your data according to the General Data Protection Regulation. (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016.

Responsible: HarvRESt Consortium

Purpose: Your data may be used under your consent, to participate in this event. Once the data is analysed, a report of the findings may be submitted. The project's deliverables that may be derived from this **activity will not include your data** or any other information that could identify you. The results of this project activity may be also shared with European Union representatives (e.g., the Project Officer evaluating the project's progress, etc.) Only broad trends will be reported, and **it will not be possible to identify any individuals**. No risks are involved.

Exercise your rights: According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), you are entitled to exercise your rights of access, rectification, elimination, limitation, opposition, and portability and to not be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing by contacting by email to info@foodbiocluster.dk. If you wish to access detailed information on how the HarvRESt project handles data, you might check the HarvRESt Privacy Policy Project. (<https://www.harvrest.eu/privacy-policy/>).

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my data needed for:

(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that you do not consent to that specific subject).

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	I have been informed about the treatment of my data (mandatory)	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	I consent to participate in the first round of Warm-up events to learn more about RES integration at the farm level (mandatory)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	I am interested in joining other HarvRESt activities (optional)	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	I wish to receive newsletters about the dissemination activities of HarvRESt (optional)	<input type="checkbox"/>

 Name of participant

 Date

 Signature

ACRONYM	HarvREST
PROJECT NAME	Harnessing the vast potential of RES for sustainable farming
PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-7
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
PROJECT NUMBER	101136904
START DAY	1 January 2024
DURATION	36 months

7.2.13 Brainstorming material ideas

If your Use Case opts to have co-creation sessions as part of the Warm-up events, an indicative set of questions is provided below:

For **local community actors**:

- How aware are you of the benefits of renewable energy for local farms and the community?
- Are there any local renewable energy initiatives you are aware of or involved in?
- What are your primary concerns regarding renewable energy projects in your community?

For **farmers**:

- What are your main challenges in adopting renewable energy technologies on your farm?
- What type of support (financial, technical, informational) would most help you in transitioning to renewable energy?
- How do you think renewable energy can impact your farm's productivity and sustainability?

For **government and policy makers**:

- What policies or programs are currently in place to support renewable energy adoption in agriculture?
- How can local governments further incentivise or facilitate renewable energy projects for farms?
- What role do you see for renewable energy in the region's long-term agricultural and environmental strategy?

For **Renewable Energy Experts/Providers**:

- What are common barriers you see farmers facing in adopting renewable energy, and how can they be overcome?
- Can you share examples of successful renewable energy projects at the farm level?
- What incentives or programs are available to help farmers finance renewable energy installations?
- How can renewable energy solutions be tailored to meet the specific needs of small and large farms?

For **Medium and Large-Sized Energy Industries**:

- Can you provide examples of successful projects where your technologies have been implemented on farms?
- What are the primary challenges you face in deploying renewable energy solutions to farms?
- How do you address the logistical and financial barriers that farmers may encounter when adopting renewable energy technologies?

7.3 Warm-up events - Reporting template

Important note:

*This reporting template has been developed to gather the most important insights from the Warm-up events across all Use Cases. It will help all pilots to capture the information in an organised and standardised manner. The output from each Warm-up event is of key importance for other HarvRESt activities, such as the Awareness Raising Campaigns (T3.2), the Use Case Working Groups (T2.5), etc. Therefore, the expected format is **detailed paragraphs** rather than bullet points. If you have any doubts about how to fill in this Template, please contact the HarvRESt WR team.*

After the end of each event, the organisers should fill in the **event reporting template** (also shared via e-mail and uploaded in the SharePoint repository) and send it to WR. The template requires the information enlisted below:

1. Workshop General Information

- Title:
- Date :
- Venue :
- Organiser(s) :
- Participants and stakeholder groups and subgroups represented*⁶

2. Detailed remarks from the Warm-up event

This section of the report must reflect the pivotal importance of the warm-up event and provide rich and detailed information on the stakeholder's contributions. If your Use Case includes an interactive session (see section 3 of the Warm-up Guidelines), particular attention should be paid to stakeholders' insights and feedback. In that sense, **please do not use bullet points but describe in elaborated paragraphs** as needed.

- Event's goals, objectives, and relevance to HarvRESt

{Reporting text}

- Organisation of the event⁷

{Reporting text}

- Outcomes of the event

Please present here the main outcomes of the event, if there were any new ideas generated, if there were any outcomes relevant to the stakeholder engagement process

{Reporting text}

- Evaluation of the event

⁶ Limited to stakeholder groups and subgroups. Not personal data is required for the implementation of this task.

⁷ Please briefly describe the preparatory actions that you followed for organising the workshop. Please also provide here a list of the supporting material used during the workshop implementation. Include your feedback/experience on the use of specific online platforms and e-tools.

Please indicate here the key takeaways from this event/activity. You can find here some questions that can help you to prepare this section.

- Were there any specific success factors?
- What challenges did you face with this event/activity?
- When re-deploying this event/activity would you do it differently? If so, how?
- Did participants give you any feedback?

{Reporting text}

- Other remarks

{Reporting text}

3. Workshop documentation and outreach/dissemination efforts

- Dissemination efforts

If applicable, briefly describe the dissemination and communications activities carried out before, during and after the event and the HarvRESt material distributed, if any (e.g. brochures/ posters displayed).

[Reporting text]

- Pictures and material produced during the warm-up event

- Include here or attach to this report pictures of the warm-up materials (white-board annotations, flipcharts, sticky notes, written notes, etc.). Please, also add a label indicating what material is included.
- Include here copies of the materials used to promote the event ((e.g. links to press releases, videos, posts, leaflets, etc.)
- Include here pictures of the event. Please, only include pictures from participants who provided **explicit consent** to have their images taken during the warm-up events.

Provide also as attachment:

- Minutes
- All Presentations (if applicable)
- The agenda of the event
- Any other relevant material